

REINCARNATE

D2.1 - Lean Construction Resource Planning

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

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D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Abstract

Deliverable D2.1 focuses on integrating Lean Construction Resource Planning principles with digital technology Building Information Modelling to optimize resource use, minimize waste, and report and reduce carbon footprints on construction sites.

Within the Task 2.1 Lean construction resource planning, the perspectives of the general contractor and the material producer were taken into account to develop concepts of active waste reduction during construction work. This led to the development digital tools: a BIM-integrated plug-in for concrete ordering, streamlining the process from order to delivery, and enabling real-time tracking of the carbon footprint associated with concrete. This is achieved via innovative connection of Digital Delivery Tickets with BIM model. Additionally, a functionality was developed in Circular Potential Information Management platform to allow automatized parametrisation of a model in open-standards environment.

By leveraging data from Environmental Product Declarations, integrating them with existing documents and BIM tools, the project demonstrates the potential for automated, real-time carbon reporting and waste reduction, ultimately promoting sustainability in the construction sector.

Keywords

Carbon footprint, LCA, Lean resource planning, Waste reduction, BIM, Concrete Delivery Ticket, EPD, parametrisation, CP-IM

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BREEAM	BRE Environmental Assessment Method
BRP	Building Renovation Passport
bSDD	buildingSmart Data Dictionary
CDE	Common Data Environment
CDW	Construction And Demolition Waste
CEMEX, CEMX	Project Partner Cemex
CO2e, CO2eq	Carbon Dioxide Equivalent
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Management
DDT	Digital Delivery Ticket
DEMO	Project Partner DEMO Consultants
EPC	Energy Performance Certificates
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
ESIF	The European Structural And Investment Funds
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, And Air Conditioning.
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
IT	Information Technology
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
LEED	Leadership In Energy And Environmental Design (Rating)
MEPS	Minimum Energy Performance Standards
MOS	Project Partner Mostostal Warszawa
NBRP	National Building Renovation Plan
PE	Primary Energy
PM	Particulate Matter
QR	Quick-Response Code
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UI	User Interface
UIA	Urban Innovative Actions
WLC	Whole Life-Cycle Carbon

Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of construction and demolition waste (CDW) — representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe —, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019 — Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market — and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

3 empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains.

All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

List of Content

List of Figures and Tables	9
1. Introduction	11
1.1. Structure of the Deliverable 2.1	11
1.2. Term of the lean construction resource planning	12
1.2.1. Relatedness of the term with the task being reported	12
1.2.2. Key Principles of Lean Construction Resource Planning	12
1.3. The Significance of Carbon Footprint in Reincarnate's Objectives	13
1.3.1. Current methodology for estimating the carbon footprint of buildings	14
1.3.2. Carbon footprint calculation in Poland	19
1.4. Decarbonisation roadmap	21
1.4.1. Decarbonisation roadmap in Europe	22
1.4.2. Decarbonisation roadmap in Poland	24
1.4.3. Financial aspect of the decarbonisation in Poland and EU	29
2. Problem statement	32
2.1. Actual state of the art of concrete ordering and delivery	32
2.2. Storing Carbon footprint information in BIM Models - Current state of the art	36
2.3. Conclusion	38
3. Development and Outcomes	40
3.1. Objectives	40
3.2. CEMEX BIM + GO Solution	42
3.2.1. Conceptualising the development of digital tools	42
3.2.2. Technical description of the development of IT solution	43
3.2.3. Functionalities of the CEMEX solution	47
3.2.4. Further development of Cemex tool	56
3.3. CP-IM platform	59

4. Challenges and Opportunities	64
4.1. Revit BIM model creation – geometry focus	64
4.2. Revit BIM model creation – information layer assignment.....	64
4.3. IFC model – information layer assignment	69
4.4. Assigning properties – other practical tests of openBIM usage.....	72
4.5. Challenges Faced by Concrete Manufacturers During Integration Testing of Ordering Tool with BIM Tool.....	74
4.6. Challenges in applying the ontology – CP-IM.....	76
5. Scalability and Planned Demonstrations	77
5.1. Scalability	77
5.1.1. Scalable to other construction materials and elements.....	77
5.1.2. Scalability thanks to open standards	77
5.2. Initial demonstration/ validation plan.....	78
5.2.1. Virtual Demonstration #1 – Faculty of Psychology	79
5.2.2. Virtual Demonstration #2 – Waste Water Treatment Plant, Albacete	84
5.2.3. Real Demonstration – Urzut.....	87
6. Innovation value	89
6.1. Innovation value for Contractor – MOS	89
6.2. Innovation value for Concrete Manufacturer - CEMEX.....	90
7. Conclusions	91

Appendix 1. CEMEX GO + BIM – workflow process map

List of Figures and Tables

Figure 1 Upcoming changes in legislation in Poland	20
Figure 2 The examples of documents used to track the concrete orders	33
Figure 3 Diagram of an extension of the current project concrete procurement process.	36
Figure 4 Innovation level of the concept of real-time parametrisation of carbon footprint based on the Concrete Delivery Tickets	40
Figure 5 Assigned parameters to the element	44
Figure 6 Visualisation of order tickets in the user interface and in PDF format	46
Figure 7 Assigning material to the element	47
Figure 8 Alert pop-up window, when ordered volume is 1.5 than initial volume	48
Figure 9 Choosing element and material to order	48
Figure 10 Creation of the order in 4 steps	50
Figure 11 Change of the status of the order	53
Figure 12 Assigning parameters to the element	54
Figure 13 Parameters assigned to the element	56
Figure 14 Developed scenarios depending on the number of Concrete Delivery Tickets and the number of elements to be parameterised	57
Figure 15 Example of main notions and IFC counterparts in purple boxes	61
Figure 16 Sequence diagram for creating a DDT QR-code	63
Figure 17 Screenshots of scanning a DDT QR-code and updating an IFC-file in RE OnSite	63
Figure 18 The output of opening an IFC file exported from ArchiCAD in Revit: a model partially exported with damaged geometry.	64
Figure 19 The IFC ontology prepared by partner DEMO - selected parameters crucial for model information layer	65
Figure 20 Dynamo script for creating parameters in Revit from the Excel file.	66
Figure 21 The Dynamo script for the calculation of 'GWP gross [kgCO ₂ eq]' and 'GWP net [kgCO ₂ eq]'	67
Figure 22 Revit 'Material Browser' interface, which does not allow users to create their own material properties..	67

Figure 23 Parameters from the IFC ontology created as instance parameters in Revit and grouped into existing Revit parameter groups.	68
Figure 24 The user-friendly usage of the Dynamo script for calculating the GWP of each model element requires only clicking the 'Play' button.	69
Figure 25 IfcMaterial properties editing panel in Blender - Bonsai plug-in: the previous unintuitive way of displaying properties.	70
Figure 26 IfcMaterial properties editing panel in Blender - Bonsai plug-in, updated after MOS consultations with the Bonsai plug-in developers.	70
Figure 27 The IFC model with the IfcMaterial parameters added to the selected model elements.	71
Figure 28 The IFC model displayed in BIMcollab ZOOM with IfcMaterial parameters included.	72
Figure 29 The process of assigning classification to model elements with the use of bSDD plug-in for Revit – step 1 – selection of the element (structural column).	73
Figure 30 The process of assigning classification to model elements with the use of bSDD plug-in for Revit – step 2 – choosing the proper class from the bSDD dictionary and assigning properties and property sets.	73
Figure 31 The process of assigning classification to model elements with the use of bSDD plug-in for Revit – step 3 –properties and property sets assigned to the model element (structural column), visible in the Properties window in Revit.	74
Figure 32 Fragment of ontology established within WPI regarding concrete parameters	76
Figure 33 The view of an IFC model used in the construction and Revit model prepared specifically for REINCARNATE	80
Figure 34 View of the WWTP of Albacete construction works, Albacete	84
Figure 35 Views of the BIM model of the biological reactor, Albacete	85
Figure 36 The current state and the planned extension of the Urzut machine storage park	87
Figure 37 Some of the concrete rubble samples tested in laboratory in Urzut within REINCARNATE	88
Table 1 Preliminary list of testing scenarios	82

1. Introduction

1.1. Structure of the Deliverable 2.1

Deliverable D2.1 focuses on integrating Lean Construction Resource Planning principles with digital technology Building Information Modelling to optimize resource use, minimize waste, and report and reduce carbon footprints on construction sites. The report begins with the **Introduction**. Here the essential background information is provided. This section starts with an explanation of the core concept of lean construction resource planning, including its key principles. Then the aspect of the carbon footprint minimisation in construction is given, emphasizing its significance in achieving the objectives of the Reincarnate. For the context also the methodology for estimating carbon footprints is covered. Finally in the introduction, the decarbonisation roadmaps for both EU and Poland are explained to show, how the lean construction resource planning concepts and solutions are in linssse with the foreseen changes in legislation.

The current challenges in the construction industry related to concrete ordering, delivery, and carbon footprint management and their toll for sustainability are then identified in the **Problem statement** section. The state of the art of the ordering process, differentiating between construction sites that use digital tools versus those that do not is described and currently available methods for storing the carbon footprint information in BIM models are outlined. In the **Development and Outcomes** section finally the chosen concepts for Lean Construction Resource Planning are identified and the development of the solutions aimed to bringing these concepts into live is described. The functionality of the CEMEX BIM + GO solution developed so far is presented in detail and the work on integration of these concepts in the openBIM environment of the CP-IM platform is given. In the **Challenges and Opportunities** sections various technical challenges that were encountered in the development of the tools are described, as well as how they were addressed.

Though the solutions developed within this tasks were related to concrete, the concepts can be scaled up and adapted to other construction materials and elements. This along with initial demonstration and validation plans on Reincarnate demonstrations sites is discussed in the **Scalability and Planned Demonstrations**

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

section. In the end the **Innovation value** for both the Concrete Manufacturer and Contractor are presented.

1.2. Term of the lean construction resource planning

1.2.1. Relatedness of the term with the task being reported

This report concerns task T2.1, which outcome was to “develop Lean Construction Resource Planning concepts and methods for active waste reduction during construction work”¹. In compliance with the Description of Action, the task directs attention to the aspect of “using building information within the CP-IM for planning construction works better to reduce scrap material and over-purchasing of materials and products due to inaccurate quantity estimates and take-offs, including carbon inventorisation”². Secondly, the task addresses the topic of the creation of solutions for reporting information about construction waste to the CP-IM platform for the purpose of enabling the development of comprehensive, cross-project strategic plans for waste management in the long term perspective.

As the task introduces the term of lean construction resource planning, it should be thoroughly investigated in order to ensure its adequate application in the task’s solutions.

1.2.2. Key Principles of Lean Construction Resource Planning

The conception of lean construction resource planning, being the intersection of “lean construction” and “resource planning” aims at maximising process value for the customer while focusing on reducing 8 types of waste, such as: defects, overproduction, waiting, not utilising talent, transport, inventory, motion, over-processing.³ Aspects that appear to be most crucial for the Reincarnate project are: overproduction, understood as inaccurate estimation of the material needed, resulting in the creation of construction waste; waiting – interpreted as waiting of the workers, ready to work while necessary materials have not been delivered on time to the construction site; transport - the delivery of materials to the construction site in advance of the actual need and last but not least - inventory – regarding materials not

¹ Description of Action – Reincarnate Project

² Description of Action – Reincarnate Project

³ Taiichi, O. (1988). Toyota Production System. New York, NY: Productivity Press. pp. XV. ISBN 0-915299-14-3.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

immediately required that constitute excess inventory, necessitating storage, leading to their degradation and imposing constraints on the budget.

The term lean construction resource planning can be aligned with sustainability goals. It intersects with not only practices such as recycling and repurposing materials and construction elements at the end of their life cycle, but can create much greater impact already at the design phase. Rethinking the way that materials are produced and construction supply chain is organised can lead to significant waste minimisation. Lean Construction Resource Planning favours materials and processes aligned with sustainability goals.

1.3. The Significance of Carbon Footprint in Reincarnate's Objectives

According to the EU definition, the term "carbon footprint" refers to the "overall quantity of CO₂ and other greenhouse gas emissions caused directly and indirectly by a product or an activity, or associated with the activities of an individual or an organisation"⁴. In the context of the construction industry, it should be understood as an estimation of the total greenhouse gas emissions over the full life cycle of a building.

The Reincarnate project focuses on the management of waste by extending the lifetime of buildings, products, and materials, emphasising their reuse. The overall goal is to set new course in terms of the sustainable building sector. To achieve this, the project aims at establishing circular value planning and modular dismantling planning methods, utilising the possibilities offered by BIM technology. Additionally, it employs methods such as lean construction resource planning, on-site valuation, and the separation of construction waste to enable and facilitate the reuse of scrap material. One of the key strategic orientations of the Reincarnate project is formulated as "Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral, and sustainable economy (Key Strategic Orientation C)"⁵ which is inextricably linked to the goal of reducing the carbon footprint of buildings.

Specifically, Work Package 2 (WP2) aims to innovate and extend cycles, delivering a BIM-supported process model to minimise waste. It develops methods for the reuse

⁴ European Court of Auditors (2014) 'How do the EU institutions and bodies calculate, reduce and offset their greenhouse gas emissions?'

⁵ Description of Action – Reincarnate Project, page 6

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

of materials, construction products, and solutions for upgrading construction products (such as windows, facade elements, and HVAC components) for reuse. These aspects are intended to significantly contribute to the reduction of the carbon footprint. The chapter 3, reporting solutions, elaborated within the project, addresses the problem of the carbon footprint directly. The first use case, developed within the Work Package 2 (WP2) involves real-time parametrisation of the carbon footprint based on Concrete Delivery Tickets and automated ordering of the concrete mix. The second use case focuses on the possibility of choosing materials based on the carbon footprint in BIM models.

1.3.1. Current methodology for estimating the carbon footprint of buildings

Based on the results of the LCA analysis, strategies can be developed to reduce the carbon footprint of a building, such as improving energy efficiency or using lower-emitting materials. To carry out this type of analysis as part of the project, we need an Environmental Product Declaration (EPD), a document that provides detailed information on the environmental impact of a product throughout its life cycle. The EPD is based on a life cycle analysis (LCA) and makes it possible to compare different products in terms of their environmental impact.

EPD certification provides transparent and comparable information about the environmental impact of a product at different stages of its life cycle.

EPD declarations comply with the standards: ISO 14025:2006 Environmental labels and declarations - Type III environmental declarations - Principles and procedures and EN 15804 - Sustainability of buildings. Environmental product declarations. Basic principles for the categorisation of construction products.

The aim of this report is not to provide new ideas for changes in legislation regarding the calculation of the carbon footprint for buildings; nevertheless, the authors find it pertinent to mention the methods of its calculation.

The current methodology for estimating the carbon footprint of buildings is based on **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** and standards - **EN 15978** (methodology for the environmental evaluation of buildings) and **EN 15804** (methodology for the environmental evaluation of construction products), as well as on **EU Level(s) system**,

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

and second edition of the publication of The Institute of Structural Engineers titled: **“How to calculate embodied carbon”**⁶

The LCA methodology divides the calculation into several **LCA modules**, corresponding to the phases of the building life – extraction and transport of raw materials and production (modules A1-A3), product transport and construction (modules A4-A5), operation, maintenance and repair (modules B1-B3), replacement and refurbishment (B4-B5), energy and water consumption (modules B6-B7), demolition and transport of waste and its disposal or treatment (modules C1-C4), benefits and loads beyond the building life cycle (module D). The majority of the above mentioned modules are part of the following **LCA stages**, forming a structure of calculations: the product stage, the construction process stage, the use stage, the end of life stage.

The decision about the phases considered in carbon footprint estimation is crucial, as it significantly influences the outcome. When shortening the calculation period, the number of establishments is limited. For the most comprehensive estimation of the carbon footprint, it is necessary to assume a building's lifetime, typically defined at 50 to 60 years. This highlights the importance of not only considering data related to the production of materials used in construction but also making assumptions about the building's usage phase in the coming decades and its end-of-life scenario⁷.

1.3.1.1 Level(s) Framework: Mandatory Life Cycle Assessment in the Design Phase

As mentioned earlier, the European Union's sustainable building indicator system, named Level(s), distinguishes three levels of life cycle assessment corresponding to different phases of the investment process: stage 1 - conceptual design, stage 2 - technical (construction) design, and stage 3 - construction and as-built stage. The second stage is obligatory, while the remaining two are recommended. **The mandatory assessment performed at the stage of technical (construction) design** is based on the project's multi-discipline documentation, especially BIM models. This allows for a precise evaluation of the quantity of projected solutions and introduces some choice criteria for the building materials to be purchased. **Methodology of**

⁶ Estimating the carbon footprint of buildings. Whole life carbon roadmap for Poland 2050. #Building Life, PLGBC, October 2022, page 13

⁷ Estimating the carbon footprint of buildings. Whole life carbon roadmap for Poland 2050. #Building Life, PLGBC, October 2022

carbon footprint calculation, presented in the latter part of this chapter primarily refers to the stage of technical (construction) design phase of the project⁸.

1.3.1.2 *Simplified Carbon Footprint Assessment Method for Buildings*

Simplified method takes into consideration modules A1-A3, that refers to the production phase and module B6, that concerns operational emissions per CO₂e

Modules A1-A3 (upfront carbon -> product stage):

The production phase constitutes the most crucial component of the life cycle assessment of a building and usually exceeds 50% of the embedded carbon footprint in the entire life cycle of the building. The calculation is based on summing up emissions for each of the elements.

For calculations, it is necessary to use a quantitative list of building materials and equipment and averaged data for products (generic) or detailed data for products, taken from EPD. The method requires consideration of all building elements, including the underground structure, construction of the above-ground part, building envelope, internal partitions, interior surface finishes, sanitary facilities and luminaires, building installations, and equipment. The calculations involve summing up the carbon footprint corresponding to each element, according to the formula: the quantity of material used (expressed in units such as kg, m², m³) multiplied by the value of the indicator, specific to the module to which the building part is classified.

For calculations performed at the building project stage, the current EPD (Environmental Product Declaration) in accordance with PN EN 15804 should be utilised. These declarations provide information about the environmental impact of construction products, materials, and appliances. The data about CO₂ value related to the biogenic carbon stored in the product should also be indicated in the declaration.

The data about CO₂ value related to the biogenic carbon stored in the product should also be indicated in the EPD declaration.

When calculating the carbon footprint, within modules A1-A3, one should take into account the phenomenon of CO₂ sequestration, and present the value of stored carbon separately, without including it in the GWP fossil balance.

⁸ ibid

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

It is important to note that building components, whose proportion of mass does not exceed 1% of the total building mass, may be excluded from the calculation. The condition is as follows: the combined percentage of excluded elements does not surpass 5% of the building mass.

Module B6 (operational carbon -> operational energy use stage):

The share of the operational carbon footprint in the total carbon footprint of a building can range from 20% to even 80%, depending on the building type and the degree of decarbonisation of the energy network. Operational emissions should be calculated on the basis of building's demand for final energy in accordance with the methodology of energy performance certificate of a building. The amount of greenhouse gas emissions constituting the operational carbon footprint (module B6) should be determined for one year⁹.

1.3.1.3 Full Carbon Footprint Assessment Method for Buildings

The full method refers to phases A1-A5, B1-B4, B6, C1-C4 taking into account emissions in the manufacturing, usage, and end-of-life phases, as well as operational emissions, converted to CO_{2e}

In this method, **modules A1 – A3 (upfront carbon -> product stage)** should be calculated according to the principles of the simplified method.

Modules A4-A5 (upfront carbon -> construction process stage):

The A4 module focuses on CO₂ emissions resulting from material transportation from the manufacturing site to the construction site and does not have significant impact on the embedded carbon footprint – may be accelerated on the level of 1%. Information about the distance between the manufacturing and construction site, including temporary storage or transshipment locations, is required. Factors influencing CO₂ calculations include the transport mode and its emission factor expressed in the unit kgCO₂/kg/km. The weight of the transported material is also crucial. These data should be estimated based on accessible tables designed for typical transport modes and distances in each region.

Module A5 addresses the percentage of products wasted on the construction site that cannot be reused and constitutes approximately 5% of the overall embodied carbon.

⁹ ibid

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

For the calculation, waste surcharge values for each material type are extracted from specific tables. Additionally, this module requires the inclusion of temporary works and structures, such as excavation shoring.

Modules B1 – B4 (use stage embodied carbon):

Subsequently the modules B1 – B4, that concerns carbon emissions arising from the use of a building, have to be calculated. Module B1 refers exactly to the use, B2 to the maintenance, B3 to the repair and B4 to the replacement actions.

In modules B1 – B3, in case detailed data is lacking, emissions can be assumed at a level of 5-10 kg CO₂e/m². In module B4, concerning the replacement of building components, it is essential to adopt a standard time for their use in accordance with accessible tables.

Module B6 (operational carbon stage):

Module B6 covers CO₂ emissions resulting from the operation of systems integrated with the building, such as heating, ventilation, cooling, domestic hot water, or lighting. Operational emissions should be calculated with guidelines of the simplified method. For these calculations, building energy model, dynamic thermal simulations or energy calculations may be used. Results for this module B6 have to be presented separately from embedded carbon.

Modules C1-C4 (end of life stage):

Modules C1-C4 concern CO₂ emissions resulting from dismantling activities, as well as the transportation, processing, and disposal of materials after the building's use. Their contribution is usually relatively small. For the purpose of assessing the life cycle of buildings, it is recommended to adopt a 50-year operating period.

In module C1, the calculation should use an average emission factor of 3.4 kgCO₂e/m² of the total building area. The value of module C2, related to CO₂ emissions from waste transport, is mainly influenced by the distance of the waste disposal site from the building being dismantled. The average emission value for road transport over 50 meters should be assumed at 0.005 kgCO₂e per kg of transported waste. Module C3 pertains to emissions associated with the reuse or recycling of materials, while C4

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

indicates emissions resulting from the utilization process. If EPD data for these phases are not available, a substitute coefficient of 0.013 kgCO₂e/kg should be applied¹⁰.

1.3.1.4 Modules not taken into account in the calculations

Module B5 refers to emissions arising from anticipated refurbishment of the building. In practice, emissions connected to this module may be calculated within module B4.

Module B7 is related to water consumption; therefore it should not be taken into account when calculating the carbon footprint of a building.

Module D refers to the carbon footprint beyond the life cycle and present a challenge. Consequently, it should be reported separately, focused on end-of-life scenarios, promoting circularity, and highlighting recycling potential¹¹.

1.3.1.5 Results of the LCA analysis

The obtained results may be presented according to the main categories of building elements and construction works, as well as LCA phases, and should be depicted in the form of a table or chart. For a comprehensive comparison of LCA for buildings and the assessment of their greenhouse gas emission intensity during their life cycle, **the results need to be related to the total surface area of the building, expressed in m².**

What is to note is the fact that **LCA of buildings may be compared only ensuring the relative scope of the assessment.** The assessment always have to be considered in the context of the country and region where a building is located, as well as climate zone, defined in relation with heating and cooling days. Building type and year of construction is also crucial. Number of people using the building and its operational hours should also be take into consideration. Also special features, especially double façade are not without influence on the assessment of the building¹².

1.3.2. Carbon footprint calculation in Poland

As a member of the European Union, in accordance with Fit for 55, Poland is obligated to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030. As a signatory of the Paris Agreement, Poland must ensure that net global greenhouse gas emissions reach 0

¹⁰ ibid

¹¹ ibid

¹² ibid

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

by 2050. In current Polish law, the term 'carbon footprint' does not appear. However, there are concrete plans for legislation, and everything indicates that starting from 2027, all buildings with an area exceeding 2000 m² will be required to have their Whole Life Carbon calculated. Additionally, from 2030, this obligation will extend to all buildings. While regulations for the methodology of carbon footprint calculation have not been incorporated into legislation at this time, this suggests that in the coming years, there will be a need to define calculation principles and establish a database for all building materials required for the calculations.

Figure 1 Upcoming changes in legislation in Poland

1.4. Decarbonisation roadmap

Decarbonisation is described as a “process of reducing carbon dioxide (and other greenhouse gas) emissions into the atmosphere by the economies of all member states”¹³. It is inextricably linked to the concept of climate neutrality, being an objective of this process, specifically tailored to “achieve zero net greenhouse gas emissions (net zero carbon footprint)”¹⁴. For the purpose of this report, it is essential to precisely define several terms, that will be further elaborated. The term “zero net greenhouse gas emissions”, synonymous with “net zero carbon footprint” includes the term “net zero”, indicating a balance between gas emissions and removals,¹⁵. Following this expression, a net zero carbon building may be defined as “a building whose operational and embodied carbon balance, over its entire life cycle, is zero”¹⁶. Two terms should be introduced here: embodied carbon – understood as “the entire carbon footprint associated with material flows throughout the life cycle (e.g. construction, remodelling or demolition processes)”¹⁷, and operational carbon – “refers to the emissions associated with the operation of a building and the resulting energy consumption”¹⁸. The combined value of **both embodied and operational carbon footprint is referred to as the whole life carbon footprint**. Furthermore, in the context of decarbonisation, one more term needs to be introduced: “Building life cycle” – is defined in EN 15978, referring to the entire life of a building, encompassing the following life cycle phases: production phase, construction phase, use phase and end of life phase¹⁹.

The term of a ‘roadmap’ in the context of decarbonisation is used to depict and navigate the complexity of the challenge of decarbonising construction sector²⁰. It refers to the holistic plan of pathways and milestones and specific actions indispensable to achieve this goal, embedding them in a specific timeframe²¹. In the reality where the construction sector assumes responsibility for 38% of global CO₂e emissions, the decarbonisation roadmap concerns the CO₂e emissions, aroused

13 Kuczera, A. and Płoszaj - Mazurek M. (2021) ‘Whole-life-carbon-roadmap-for-Poland-2050’, PLGBC, (June), p. 11

14 ibid

15 <https://netzeroclimate.org/what-is-net-zero-2/>, access date: 23.11.2023

16 Kuczera, A. and Płoszaj - Mazurek M. (2021) ‘Whole-life-carbon-roadmap-for-Poland-2050’, PLGBC, (June), p. 9

17 ibid, p. 11

18 ibid

19 ibid

20 Kuczera, A. and Płoszaj - Mazurek M. (2021) ‘Whole-life-carbon-roadmap-for-Poland-2050’, PLGBC, (June)

21 <https://www.engieimpact.com/capabilities/decarbonization-strategy-roadmap#>, access date: 28.12.2023

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

during the whole building life cycle. Success key for the achievement of the climate neutrality is the cooperation and engagement of different stakeholders, such as government and authorities, financial institutions, associations, developers and investors, contractors, manufacturers of materials and technology providers, designers and building managers. Their partnership across the whole value chain is crucial for achieving the success²².

1.4.1. Decarbonisation roadmap in Europe

1.4.1.1 Actual situation of the building stock in Europe

Currently, EU members are concentrating their efforts to address the pressing environmental needs. Several countries have made declarations regarding carbon dioxide emissions and carbon neutrality, with some being more stringent than EU regulations. For example, Finland aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2035, and Germany has set a target of achieving carbon neutrality by 2045. Nevertheless, there are still member states facing a significant journey to reach the EU's climate goals²³.

1.4.1.2 Decarbonisation effort in European legislation

Among legal instruments, legislative practices, and initiatives aimed at **achieving climate neutrality by 2050**, the European Union has undertaken various measures, including the EU Green Deal. An interim objective within this framework is the **reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by a minimum of 55% (in comparison to 1990 levels) by 2030, known as the "Fit for 55 package."** An integral component of this initiative is the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, comprising a suite of policies designed to empower local authorities to enhance buildings' energy efficiency and upgrade the current building stock.

The proposed legislation determine that, starting in 2030, newly constructed buildings will be mandated to undergo comprehensive whole life-cycle carbon (WLC) emissions calculations. Minimum energy performance standards (MEPS) for buildings have also been implemented. The European Union has outlined the harmonization of energy performance certificates (EPCs) across all Member States by 2025, and similarly, the introduction of renovation passports (BRPs) is expected to be implemented by the end of 2024.

22 Kuczera, A. and Płoszaj - Mazurek M. (2021) 'Whole-life-carbon-roadmap-for-Poland-2050', PLGBC, (June)

23 Nugent, A. (2022) 'EU Policy Whole Life Carbon Roadmap #Buildinglife', World Green Building Council, (May), pp. 16-17

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Another program, the Circular Economy Action Plan, emphasizes waste prevention and the optimal utilization of construction and building resources for as long as possible. Within the framework of this project, two legislative propositions were introduced: the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation and the revised Construction Products Regulation. Additionally, the classification of sustainable investments (taxonomy) was implemented in June 2020. This defines clear criteria for designating a new building or one undergoing renovation as sustainable, facilitating the determination of whether the investment aligns with climate neutrality objectives. It is essential to mention the voluntary reporting framework, Level(s), which provides indicators for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings throughout their entire life cycle²⁴. These indicators focus on various aspects, including greenhouse gas emissions, resource efficiency, circular material life cycles, adaptation and resilience to climate change, optimised life cycle cost and value, as well as the creation of healthy and comfortable spaces, and the efficient use of water resources²⁵.

1.4.1.3 European decarbonisation roadmap

The European decarbonisation roadmap is manifested through successive steps on the timeline. The objectives for the years **2021-2023** include creating a plan to ensure that new buildings achieve net-zero whole-life carbon status by 2030, along with providing specific definitions of related terminology. By 2024, there will be a revision of national building renovation plans (NBRP) to ensure the attainment of net-zero emissions buildings by 2050 in all Member Countries. During this year, Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) reports will be mandated to include primary energy demand and operational carbon emissions. The EPC database is expected to be updated to digital platforms, allowing interoperability with digital building logbooks and other building data. Additionally, a Building Renovation Passport (BRP) focused on low-carbon emission renovations will be introduced, along with Minimum Energy Performance Standards that all buildings must meet.

In the second step, lasting from **2023 to 2025**, common EU product categories will be implemented, and the preparation of LCA impact and an EU carbon database will be executed. All public buildings will be obliged to undergo LCA analysis linked to a

²⁴ ibid

²⁵ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/levels/lets-meet-levels/how-does-levels-work_en; access date: 16.11.2023

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Building Renovation Plan. By 2025, newly created buildings are required to be net-zero operational carbon, with a whole-life carbon limit introduced, totalling 80% of the current level. This year also serves as a deadline for Member Countries for the first update of NBRP, containing the strategy toward whole-life carbon footprint reduction. The step is also geared towards researching how the introduction of a renovation passport would stimulate renovations executed with whole-life carbon optimisation. By 2025, the renovation passport will have been implemented into regulatory instruments such as mandatory minimum performance standards and financial instruments, including subsidies for investments that meet the criteria. Regulations requiring the acquisition of a building renovation passport by the owners of the worst-performing buildings will come into force.

In the following years – in **2026**, a strong governance body aimed at the verification of NBRP will be established. The highest Energy Performance Certificate will be synonymous with net-zero operational carbon standards. By **2028**, the whole-life carbon limit will be restricted to 60% of the starting level. Starting from **2030**, the Environmental Product Declaration will be obligatory for construction products without exception. Then, by **2031**, the whole-life carbon limit will be further restricted to 40% of the starting level. Two years later, it will be reduced to 20% of the starting level, and by 2036, all new buildings will be obliged to be net-zero carbon (whole-life zero emission buildings), as well as buildings under deep renovation. The set aim is that by **2050**, all European buildings will be net-zero WLC, and the digital building logbook will be a database containing data about the origin and quality of materials, products, data concerning the building value chain, and lifecycle.

1.4.2. Decarbonisation roadmap in Poland

1.4.2.1 Actual situation of the building stock in Poland

The Polish building stock comprises nearly 14 million buildings and is characterised by a distributed ownership structure, posing challenges in reaching building owners and consequently impeding funding for modernisation initiatives. Data indicates that almost 80% of the Polish building stock is owned by private individuals, representing one of the highest levels in Europe. Examining the percentage share in building typology, single-family houses take the lead (39.5%), followed by production, utility, and warehouse buildings (36%), uninhabited housing (17.5%), multi-family residential development (4%), and public service buildings (3%). The total surface area of all these

buildings in Poland amounts to more than 1,5 million square meters. Their energy efficiency standards are characterised by wide diversity, correlating with factors such as age, technology, construction materials, and utilisation patterns. Data from 2016, regarding emissions division by building categories, indicates the highest share from residential buildings (66%), followed by buildings for agriculture, fisheries, and forestry (19%). Public utility buildings represent the smallest share at 15%. Available data suggests that about 30% of the multi-family building stock still requires modernisation. Considering the public projects currently underway and planned, the percentage of public usage buildings having undergone thermal modernisation is projected to reach 55-60% by 2025²⁶.

A major problem contributing to the relatively high CO_{2e} emissions in Poland is the dominant use of fossil fuels in the heating sector, where they are burned in low-grade boilers, leading to winter smog. This factor contributes to a situation where six Polish cities rank among the top ten European cities in terms of the number of days with exceeded permissible levels of PM concentration. In relation to emissions from all sectors associated with the building industry (power engineering, construction and processing, heating), they account for approximately 53% of all carbon dioxide emissions in Poland, which represents a significant percentage. Data from 2017 indicates that 22% of all industrial emissions in the country are attributed to processes related to cement production, and 9% to steel production. Additionally, waste generated by buildings and building processes constitutes a meaningful source of CO_{2e} emissions. A methodology capable of minimising these contributions may involve lean construction resource planning, aiming for accurate estimation of the required materials, projects for functionally adaptive buildings with a universal structural system, and maximisation of the use of dismantled and reused materials²⁷.

1.4.2.2 Polish legislation

In terms of the building stock the most important legislation document designating obligation of the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and improvement of the energy is the transformed version of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (2010/31/EU). It demands that after 31.12.2020, all new buildings are to be nearly zero energy buildings (nZEB). The definition of this building indicates the information on

²⁶ Ibid, pp. 16-19

²⁷ Ibid, pp. 19-20

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

the required level of insulation of partitions and the necessary value of the primary energy (PE) indicator, specifying the annual energy demand of the building for non-renewable primary energy. The next update of regulations is scheduled for 2028.

One of the most significant documents, the Polish Energy Policy 2040, has been in effect since February 2021 and focuses on three major aspects: a just transition, a zero-carbon energy system, and maintaining good air quality. The objective is a transition to a zero-carbon energy system, with a particular emphasis on solutions such as the development of offshore wind energy, decentralised and civic energy, and nuclear energy. As outlined in this document, both district heating and zero or low-emission individual sources are planned to meet the needs of all households, resulting in an anticipated increase in the number of connected households to around 1.5 million by 2030. The policy places a strong emphasis on supporting passive and zero-emission buildings, aiming to construct or modernise 1000 low-emission public buildings and replace 3 million heat sources in homes by 2030. Additionally, the transformation of the heating sector is scheduled to be completed by 2040²⁸.

1.4.2.3 *Decarbonisation roadmap in Poland*

As presented above, the construction situation in Poland is characterised by a significant need for retrofitting of the Polish building stock to enhance energy performance. The entire construction sector requires comprehensive changes encompassing design, material production, construction processes, and energy sources. Poland, having signed the Paris Agreement, is obligated to achieve a global net anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions level of zero by 2050. In practical terms for the construction industry, this commitment entails the decarbonisation of the construction sector by 2050. Achieving this goal aligns with the European Green Deal's flagship project, the renovation wave. The process should commence with legislative changes, followed by promotion, and both, policy and financial support for zero carbon footprint construction, which measures are crucial for bringing about the necessary transformations²⁹. The plan for the progressive decarbonisation, referred to as the decarbonisation roadmap, involves various participants in the investment process, including government and local government administration, investors, building owners, designers, manufacturers, constructors, building managers, financial

²⁸ Ibid, p. 26

²⁹ ibid

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

institutions, and professional associations. It comprises successive steps outlined below.

Until **2025**, the focus is on creating policies and regulations to develop a strategy and outline milestones for achieving whole-life net-zero carbon buildings by 2050. This involves introducing requirements for new and retrofitted buildings regarding energy performance and implementing legislation for existing building stock, a task assigned to government and local government administration. The purpose also includes developing corresponding tools, such as a database with essential data for calculating the carbon footprint of a building, emissions, energy consumption, and savings, like the Central Register of Final Energy Savings, along with the tool for its calculation. Additionally, a verification and certification system for whole-life carbon footprint analyses should be established. Crucial issues to be addressed include government incentives such as subsidies, tax reliefs, soft loans, and low-interest loans. In terms of legal policy, the implementation of the Polish Energy Policy 2040 is planned. Research steps undertaken focus on financing innovative technologies. Educational activities for local authorities, regarding circular economy and low-carbon solutions, should be conducted, along with steps toward establishing local partnerships for experience exchange. Other stakeholders include investors, developers, and building owners, who typically play a decision-making role in both the investment process and the entire roadmap. Significant steps to be taken by 2025 involve increasing knowledge and awareness of decarbonisation and outlining environmental guidelines. This may include conducting life cycle carbon footprint analyses in projects, restricting materials to those with carbon footprint calculations, and announcing operational carbon footprint data in sales offers. The creation of a decarbonisation plan for portfolios is also a key aim. Concerning designers, understood as architects, civil engineers, and consultants, it is crucial to mention that this group significantly influences the carbon footprint through material and technological solutions. Besides gaining knowledge, the goal focuses on conducting analyses of the carbon footprint, especially in the operational carbon phase (B6). For manufacturers and suppliers, by 2025, they should deliver Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) for their products or, at the very least, product emissions data compliant with the EN-15804 standard. They should also elaborate a plan to achieve net-zero carbon emissions by 2050. In terms of facility management, analysing data concerning utility consumption and making recommendations to both owners and users is crucial. Financial

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

institutions should contribute by establishing discounted financing for investments in line with EU Taxonomy requirements and other financial tools aimed at the decarbonisation process.

By **2030** there should be accomplished the following purposes. Government administration should implement legal regulations requiring the performance of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and optimization of the life cycle carbon footprint within buildings. For local government administration, achieving a zero operational carbon footprint in municipally-owned buildings is crucial, along with providing financial support (e.g., discounts, low-interest loans) for the private building sector. Investors should conduct both LCA analyses and life cycle carbon footprint optimisations for all portfolio buildings, aiming for a net zero operational carbon footprint. Additionally, they should disseminate the idea of the whole carbon footprint. Designers are permitted to design only operational net-zero carbon footprint buildings and are encouraged to actively search for materials with a lower carbon footprint. The obligatory development of digital building logbooks for designed objects is also emphasised. In the context of the Reincarnate project, it is crucial to mention the implementation of BIM technology for calculating the entire carbon footprint during the designing process. The usage of software for carbon footprint analysis and actions towards marketing them in the Polish market are essential. By 2030, manufacturers and suppliers are obligated to create Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) for products in portfolios with the highest emission indicators. They are also required to deliver a transparent labelling system for building products and aim to operationalise the principles of the circular economy. Facility managers are expected to conduct recurrent inspections and monitor building energy performance by 2030 to select appropriate methods for improvement. The contribution of financial institutions is essential, and they should have established financing tools for investments with defined carbon footprints. Simultaneously, universities, professional associations, and NGOs are tasked with updating decarbonisation roadmap targets and propagating awareness of best practices, mistakes, and problems in the implementation of net-zero carbon footprint building methods. These stakeholders, particularly universities, institutions, and NGOs, will take responsibility for developing auditing rules, case studies of complete carbon footprints calculations, and serving as advisors or collaborators in the process of preparing specific decarbonisation plans. They will also

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

create training programs concerning the term and develop BIM solutions for calculating the carbon footprint.

To the year **2040**, the following changes should be implemented. Government administration is obliged to establish a verification and certification system for carbon footprint analyses connected to the digital building register and building stock data. Local governments should proceed with creating digital logbooks for private buildings. Other members of the investment process, including developers, investors, and building owners, are required to refurbish existing buildings based on the rules outlined in decarbonisation plans written in digital building logbooks. They should also design new buildings in accordance with the concept of a whole-life net zero carbon footprint. Regarding designers, the focus should be on designing almost exclusively net-zero carbon buildings. By 2040, manufacturers should provide not only Environmental Product Declarations for some products but for all their goods. Facility managers are supposed to optimise building management processes in terms of carbon footprint indicators. The contribution of financial institutions is also essential, as they should establish financing tools for investments with a reduced carbon footprint value. In this phase of the decarbonisation roadmap, professional institutions and universities are responsible for researching design solutions that lead to the achievement of a negative carbon footprint in the construction sector.

The ultimate goal of the decarbonisation roadmap by **2050** is for all buildings to exhibit a minimal operational carbon footprint. New constructions and renovated buildings should strive for a comprehensive life cycle net-zero carbon footprint, considering both embodied and operational carbon emissions. The changes over the last 10 years of the roadmap aim for the design of exclusively net-zero carbon buildings, including those with a negative carbon footprint. By 2050, manufacturers aim to guarantee net-zero carbon emissions from the manufacture and transportation of their products. Financial support from institutions by 2050 would be restricted to investments characterised by a whole-life net-zero carbon footprint³⁰.

1.4.3. Financial aspect of the decarbonisation in Poland and EU

The Polish financial instruments address the support of building energy efficiency, the development of renewable energy, and the elimination of low emissions. The longest-

³⁰ Ibid, pp. 34-48

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

running program is the Thermo-renovation and Repairs Fund, focusing on supporting energy-efficient renovations in multi- and single-family buildings. However, it has also extended help to housing cooperatives and communities. The second program, 'Clean Air,' aims at the thermo-renovation of single-family residential buildings and co-financing the removal of old heating systems burning solid fuels. The 'My Electricity' program supports the co-financing of photovoltaic installations on a micro-scale. The 'Energy-efficient construction. Part 1) Reducing energy consumption in buildings' program aims to reduce energy consumption in buildings while increasing the production of energy from renewable sources, primarily financing public usage buildings. The Operational Programme Infrastructure and Environment, Measure 1.3, supports energy efficiency in buildings, providing repayable financial aid for thermo-renovation investments in the housing sector, as well as co-financing public utility thermo-renovation investments. Regional Operational Programmes focus on comprehensive, multi-family building deep energy-efficient renovation. The last but not least, Thermo-renovation relief, is a program offering subjective income tax exemption to owners of single-family buildings who have conducted thermo-modernisation works in them.

Unfortunately, at this moment, administrative financial support does not take into consideration zero carbon footprint projects. For that reason, the opportunity for Poland lies in taking advantage of European financing programmes³¹.

Sustainable finance can contribute to enhancing the standards of the European building stock. As part of the European Green Deal initiative, the European Union has established the Just Transition Mechanism, providing financial support to regions most affected by the changes associated with the transition to a carbon-neutral economy. This mechanism aims to mobilise around 55 billion euros solely within the years 2021-2027. Concurrently, aligning with the targets of the Paris Agreement, the EU is pursuing sustainability investment loans and sustainability-linked loans³².

As far as decarbonisation is concerned, the Sustainable Europe Investment Plan has to be mentioned. Being part of the European Green Deal, it aims at mobilising 1 billion EUR for sustainable investments. The European Structural and Investment Funds

31 Kuczera, A. and Płoszaj - Mazurek M. (2021) 'Whole-life-carbon-roadmap-for-Poland-2050', PLGBC, (June), p. 32

32 Nugent, A. (2022) 'EU Policy Whole Life Carbon Roadmap #Buildinglife', World Green Building Council, (May), pp. 16, 38, 40

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

(ESIF) are instruments intended for a sustainable and healthy European environment. One of the main areas within its scope is the management of natural resources and the low-carbon economy. The LIFE program stimulates investments oriented towards energy efficiency, with a focus on European regions where this aspect is poorly developed. Urban Innovative Actions (UIA) target urbanistic solutions, providing cities with financial resources for testing new ideas to address urban challenges. URBACT III's purpose is to enable European cities to cooperate towards the exchange of experience and solutions for urban challenges. Municipal, local, and regional public authorities may benefit from the European Energy Efficiency Fund, which financially supports investments related to energy efficiency, renewable energy, and clean urban transportation³³.

³³ Kuczera, A. and Płoszaj - Mazurek M. (2021) 'Whole-life-carbon-roadmap-for-Poland-2050', PLGBC, (June), pp.28-29

2. Problem statement

The adaptation of the planned changes in EU legislation are currently hampered by limited available technology and the current practices in managing the LCA data. The ways of reporting the built-in carbon footprint of a whole building are time consuming and labour intensive. To achieve detailed built-in carbon footprint summary, it must be based on accurate Bills of Quantities created from precise Material Take-Offs. Additionally, to closely reflect true carbon footprint of a building the CO₂ values should come from a product-specific EPDs and not be based on generic data. This challenge could be resolved by creating software environment that seamlessly connects the precise information on the quantities of materials contained in a BIM model with the precise LCA unit values contained in products EPD.

Similarly, the material ordering at the construction sites is a process prone to over-ordering and in results waste creation. This caused by inaccurate Bills of Quantity and challenges in information flow between the concrete manufacturer and construction management. Especially in case of ordering concrete, overordering material often means that it has to be disposed considering the short time period when concrete mix can be cast. Additionally, if the construction management wants to transfer the information contained in Concrete Delivery Ticket to the BIM model to manage the concrete ordering process and centralize the data it has to be done manually.

Lack of technology that provides an integrated ecosystem for placing an order and transferring the exact order information into a centralised data base such as a BIM model creates a strain on the construction management, which is required to perform many processes manually.

In this section current state of art of concrete ordering and delivery is summarised as well as the current methods of integrating LCA information in BIM models. This is done to show the innovation level of the Reincarnate concepts and solutions to summarise exactly what existing problems in the industry they tackle.

2.1. Actual state of the art of concrete ordering and delivery

2.1.1. Construction sites not using digital tools supporting purchase phase

A common way of ordering concrete and managing orders documentation in Poland is without implementation of any digital tools supporting purchase. Individual steps

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

of the process are completely separated and based on person-to-person communication with a phone or an email.

Figure 2 The examples of documents used to track the concrete orders

The construction workflow begins with preparing a summary of work requirements, based on the quantities outlined in the bill of quantities. These quantities are usually extracted from either 2D documentation or a Building Information Modelling (BIM) model. The required quantities are then marked on printed construction plans and manually entered into an Excel file. This data is essential for preparing the weekly order sent to the concrete supplier, typically finalized on Fridays. The order includes the precise quantities needed for each day of the following week and specifies any additional logistics, such as whether a concrete pump or crane will be required for delivery.

On a daily basis, a construction engineer confirms material orders through a phone call. Once the order is processed and delivered, a physical ticket is issued to confirm both the delivery and the quality of the materials. Upon arrival of the concrete trucks at the construction site, delivery notes are thoroughly checked, followed by quality inspections to confirm that the material meets the specified standards. Once verified, the concrete is unloaded and utilized immediately on-site.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

In parallel, a list of delivery tickets is maintained to track and manage concrete work activities. A concrete work logbook is used to record the completed work; however, due to a lack of integration between systems, this information must be manually entered into a separate record file. If an as-built BIM model is required by the investor, parameters from the completed work must be manually transferred into the BIM model.

This approach to concrete ordering creates several challenges. If the initial estimates are inaccurate, excess concrete may be ordered, leading to waste creation, as oftentimes any surplus cannot be reused effectively. Similarly, underestimating the amount needed could require additional pours, incurring extra costs and potential delays. The manual nature of calculations and data entry increases the likelihood of errors, which can result in material shortages or surplus. Additionally, miscommunication or last-minute adjustments with the supplier can further complicate the process.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

2.1.2. Construction sites using digital tools supporting purchase phase

In the purchasing phase of a construction site, digital tools support the ordering process, supply monitoring and material logistics management. They help optimise time, cost and resource management. An existing solution at Cemex is the Cemex GO application, which has been combined with BIM (Building Information Modelling) as

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

part of the project. BIM is a tool and method for managing building information that supports the entire process of designing, constructing and operating a building. They enable the integration of data on materials and resources, which supports purchasing decisions based on accurate building models.

The project developed a combination of the CEMEX GO ordering tool with BIM and the development of a digital delivery ticket to create a cohesive project management system that reduces costs, better inventory planning, reduces construction waste and energy consumption associated with transportation. This allows projects to be delivered in a more sustainable and environmentally friendly way, resulting in more efficient construction and building lifecycle management.

Figure 3 - Diagram of an extension of the current project concrete procurement process.

2.2. Storing Carbon footprint information in BIM Models - Current state of the art

While LCA is gaining traction, it is not yet consistently applied across construction projects. It is more often conducted in the design phase of large, high-profile projects, on a case-basis with single examples of application and lack of universal solutions and practices. Conducting the analysis of the built-in carbon footprint done at the design stage of a construction project can lead to a more conscious choice of material and create awareness about the ecological costs of the construction. Though, performing

the CO₂ footprint analysis early in the project has its benefits it is also has its limitations. During the actual course of the construction significant changes to the projects can be made. Changes of material variant can happen for instance due to its availability. Additionally, losses caused by material overordering and other human error cannot be precisely accounted for during the design phase. Further limitation stem from the generic material libraries found in LCA tools. Instead of calculating the carbon footprint values from EPDs of the chosen and ordered material the calculation is often based on generic, averaged out values that may notably differ from the values estimated for the exact product. All this makes the results of such LCA analysis less reliable.

Another significant obstacle in adaptation of LCA analysis on a wider scale is the integration of the LCA software with the BIM models. A publication from the Belgian Building Research Institute³⁴ identifies 5 workflow strategies for the integration of LCA and BIM:

1. **Bill of quantities export** - Bill of Quantities take off the BIM model into the LCA software)
2. **IFC import of surfaces** - Import of a generic model to LCA software)
3. **BIM viewer for linking LCA profiles** - BIM viewer for association of LCA profiles, then the LCA calculation in the LCA software
4. **LCA plugin for BIM-software** - Integration of the LCA database and LCA profile with the use of a LCA plug-in in the BIM software
5. **LCA enriched BIM objects** - Enriching the BIM objects with the LCA profiles in the BIM software and use of a LCA plug-in in the BIM software to generate results

Most commonly used approach is exporting the Bill of Quantities from a BIM model and sending it to LCA software, where the Bill of Quantities and LCA values are combined and multiplied. The BIM models at the early stage of the design phase are characterised by a low LoD, which impacts the incompleteness of the Bill of Quantities. The data must be often manually treated in a spreadsheet before it is

³⁴Wastiels, L., Decuyper, R., 2019. Identification and comparison of LCA-BIM integration strategies. IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci. 323 (1), 012101 <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/323/1/012101>

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

finally uploaded in the LCA software³⁵ This segmented process is not only time consuming, but also error prone, in consequence it puts a remarkable stress on a part responsible for delivering LCA analysis.

On the other hand the 5th strategy which is based on enriching the BIM objects with the LCA profiles in the BIM software and conducting the LCA analysis in the BIM software with the use of a plug-in has a high potential to conveniently centralize the information within the model. In this approach, to assure the data is up-to-date connection to real-time information on the carbon footprint should be established. Moreover, assigning the material to the BIM elements should be made as convenient as possible to minimise the labour related to changing LCA information. The challenge of implementing this BIM based strategy to LCA analysis lays in lack of interoperability between the BIM model, material libraries, EPDs and LCA reporting.

2.3. Conclusion

As part of the Reincarnate project, the challenge of complying with emerging regulations mandating built-in carbon footprint reporting presents an opportunity to develop a unique system for streamlining concrete ordering and carbon footprint tracking. To address the risk of material overordering, an approach where materials are ordered directly from the BIM model using a plug-in was identified. This method aims to minimize the likelihood of errors while consolidating all relevant information within a single, centralized model. By doing so, it has the potential to simultaneously enhance transparency and optimize the workflow, offering mutual benefits to both material suppliers and construction managers. The successful implementation of this approach relies on the integration of material libraries containing precise, up-to-date data with the BIM model. As well as the plug-in to place, track the processing and delivery of the concrete order from the interface of the model

Furthermore, a connection between the carbon footprint values embedded in the EPD attributes and the BIM model is necessary to achieve LCA reporting from a BIM model. Incorporating the EPD data into the electronic Concrete Delivery Ticket was recognised as method of using this document as a data carrier. Then to finally transfer

³⁵ Parece, S.; Resende, R, Rato, V. 2024, A BIM-based tool for embodied carbon assessment using a Construction Classification System, Developments in the Built Environment, Volumes 19, ISSN 2666-1659, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dibe.2024.100467>.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

the order data to the BIM Model, there is a need for functionality that ensures the seamless transfer of LCA data from the Delivery Ticket upon the material's arrival at the construction site. Thereby parametrising accurate data, needed for reporting of the building's carbon footprint throughout the construction process.

From the perspective of Cemex as a concrete manufacturer, integrating the ordering tool with the BIM tool brings significant operational and business benefits. As the BIM started to be more and more popular amongst construction companies, we wanted to make their life easier and propose another entry point of concrete ordering. Thanks to that costumers can connect their model with our ordering tool and simply estimate the volume and type of concrete needed. Once the delivery is finished, customer can retrieve information about concrete type and its parameters together with information about delivery itself. This information might be crucial for the future maintenance of the building and all information can be stored in one place. Another point is that nowadays information about embodied CO₂ is starting to be more required due to different European regulations and green building certifications like BREEAM or LEED. Thanks to our solution, customer can easily retrieve information about the embodied CO₂ of specific concrete element and in the end summarize total embodied carbon from concrete of the whole structure.

3. Development and Outcomes

3.1. Objectives

Based on the analysis of the current state of art and the evaluation of what actions would be possible within the scope of the Task 2.1 the 3 main objectives were agreed on by CEMEX and Mostostal teams:

- (1) Creating the concept of a solution for direct material ordering from the BIM Model
- (2) Creating the concept of real-time parametrisation of carbon footprint based on the Concrete Delivery Tickets
- (3) Integrating (1) and (2) concepts with the existing Cemex concrete ordering system and BIM plug-in to in result achieve one ecosystem that bring these concepts to life in form of a functioning solution.

Figure 4 Innovation level of the concept of real-time parametrisation of carbon footprint based on the Concrete Delivery Tickets

To achieve this the preliminary scope of action was agreed (and later executed):

1. Formulation of the use cases. Defining expectations and benefits from the tools.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

2. Feedback from Mostostal Warszawa on the existing CEMEX GO application and CEMEX BIM plug-in
3. Reviewing and improving the current template of Digital Delivery Ticket (adding EPD information to current template)
4. Adjustment of the Ontology developed within T1.1
5. Choosing the parameters that should be saved in the BIM Model.
6. Establishing the final workflow of the solutions.
7. Developing the functionalities in the CEMEX ecosystem. **Creating one plug-in allowing for:**
 - 7.1. Automatic extraction of order data (Quantity Take-Off) from the BIM Model
 - 7.2. Preparation of the Bill of Quantities
 - 7.3. Scheduling the concrete deliveries
 - 7.4. Managing the status of order processing and delivery
 - 7.5. Generation of a Concrete Delivery Ticket with the CO₂ information
 - 7.6. Parametrisation of the BIM model with the carbon footprint information from the Concrete Delivery Ticket

These action points were established with the goal of creating common benefits. First, they aim to improve communication between the construction site and the concrete manufacturer. Second, they help prevent the overordering of concrete mix, which reduces waste by avoiding mistakes in the Bill of Quantities. Finally, they streamline and automate the flow of CO₂ information, centralizing this data within the BIM model.

A step towards a more universal solution was the development of a solution with DEMO consultants in the CP-IM Platform. Here the objective was to replicate the functionality of BIM Model parametrisation with information included in the Concrete Delivery in the open-standards-friendly environment of CP-IM. The aim was to integrate the workflow with CP-IM to achieve a prove of concept of streamlined information flow from a delivery ticket to an IFC model. This approach has the potential to create a single platform for processing the information contained in the various products product specification (e.g. concrete, masonry products, windows) and centralising it in a BIM model. It would mean that the concept of real-time parametrisation of carbon footprint in the BIM model could be applied in practice to any conceivable material or building component in the universal standard of IFC.

3.2. CEMEX BIM + GO Solution

3.2.1. Conceptualising the development of digital tools

One of the first steps working on this innovation was the analysis of the needs of the end user and formulation of use cases. Here over several meetings the common goals and approach was agreed. Feasible objectives as described in section **3.1 Objectives** were chosen and described in detail. Early in the project, the issue was approached in a structured way by collecting information on innovation context, planned innovation scope, preliminary development plan as well as expected results and validation. This assured that multiple members from both Mostostal and CEMEX teams were on the same page when it comes to the scope of Task 2.1 work.

Before starting the work on the development of the connection of Cemex Revit plugin and existing Cemex Go (ordering tool) Cemex team needed to prepare ourselves for the job. We decided to conduct interviews with different construction companies. In total we have conducted 9 interviews – 3 in Germany, 2 in Poland and 4 in Mexico. Companies that we have talked to are big and medium sized Engineering Construction companies and one design, business unit of corporate materials selling company. We have asked questions about their use of BIM and processes they are following from planning, designing to construction phase. Streamline ordering from BIM to Cemex Go concept has been well received among interviewees mostly because of the positive impact it could bring to multiple areas: like construction, procurement, and quality assurance. Interviewees have shared their concerns in the following areas:

- mix requirements - public contractors in Germany avoid specifying the supplier or specific material/product for quantity takeoffs. Building upon this insight, further research with UK customers for Readymix reveals that customers tend to rely on 2 to 3 Readymix suppliers, ensuring backup options in case an order cannot be fulfilled for any reason.
- model construction - Recognize that not all models align with typical construction practices, potentially leading to inaccuracies in volume measurements (e.g., 50 ft columns within a single geometry). To address this, experts suggest implementing an alert system, possibly driven by AI, prompting order-makers to

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

confirm volume accuracy or accept associated risks. This approach aims to reduce errors and enhance accountability in the ordering process.

- volume & schedule uncertainty - Ensure that any order generated from the model volume must undergo confirmation by the jobsite manager, allowing for necessary modifications based on on-site measurements and scheduling requirements.
- training - In the jobsite, the collaboration between BIM coordinators, planners, and jobsite managers will be pivotal in driving a cultural shift and facilitating successful adoption

Interviewees in general recognize the significant value of real-time CO₂ data. They also contemplate integrating this data into the construction model, foreseeing its usefulness throughout the construction phase. While some companies attempt to calculate CO₂ emissions during construction, interviewees emphasized the significant value of real-time integration within the construction model.

Another step that was made was preparation of data flow (Appendix 1) chart that was intended to help us map the process. Data flow chart guide us from the customer and BIM model creation, through the choice of concrete and its validation with contract, then to concrete production, dispatching and arrival to the jobsite, until assignation of the concrete parameters to the concreted element.

3.2.2. Technical description of the development of IT solution

Connection of Revit software to the existing Cemex Go feature, through Cemex Revit plug-in involved several key functionalities. However, to make all of that possible we have built plug-in based on Revit API, which is available to the public free of charge. It is necessary to build the code in Visual Studio, using C# language and .NET framework. In further steps it included authentication with CEMEX Go credentials inside the Revit plugin and visualization of user data such as the history of orders, customers, contacts, and jobsites. The process also features automatic validation of chosen concretes in Revit with materials agreed with customer's contract through the CEMEX Go APIs. In cases where the relationship between chosen concretes and those agreed upon in the contract was unclear, user validation was required. Additionally, there is support and contact functionality included for concretes not included in the contract.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

The process allows for the creation of orders through the CEMEX Go API and the assignment of those orders to elements in the Revit model. Existing orders could also be assigned to elements in the Revit model. It included confirmation of delivery and tracking of the order timeline, as well as retrieving corresponding data of the order through delivery tickets. Parameters of delivered concretes could be assigned to specific elements in the Revit project. At the beginning we thought that modeler should add rows for wanted parameters for the element. However, during creation process it turned out that it is easier when plug-in writes itself rows for needed parameters together with final values. This process is automated inside Cemex Revit plug-in.

Figure 5 Assigned parameters to the element

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

The process supports multiple relationships between orders and elements, including one order to one element, one order to many elements, and many orders to one element. It also includes visualization of order tickets in the user interface and in PDF format, as well as visualization of elements and their assigned orders. There is differentiation between design volume and ordered volume, and visualization of data in the CO₂ analysis tool with the delivered values.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Apply To Revit Model

Material Name: All | Order: All

Element ID	Element Name	Material Name	Volume [m3]	Assign
320502		VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	42.16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
321280		VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	42.12	<input type="checkbox"/>

Order ID	Purchase Order	Delivery Date	Status
20611267	15.10.2024	16/10/2024 09:50	In process - t

Ticket ID	Batched Date and Time	Total Delivered Quantity	Plant	Status	More Info
39512677	16/10/2024 07:24	1	PL-Kraśnik (Urzędów)	Finished	More info

Buttons: Refresh, Assign

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Customer 136371	Jobsite 1379434	Plant Name: PL-Kraśnik (Urzędów)	Ticket serial number 1024403518	Order quantity [m3] Requested 10
Mostostal Warszawa	Warszawa, ul. Pasteura/ Banacha		Date 16/10/2024 07:24:49	Released -
			Truck Number -	Difference -
Amount [m3] 1	Product VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Compressive Strength 37 MPa		
Age of Strength Class 100% at 28 days	Aggregate Size 16	Consistency Class 12 cm		
GWP Gross Product 208	GWP Gross Total 208	Exposure Classes XC4 XD1		
GWP Net Product 174 kgCO2e	GWP Net Total 174 kgCO2e	Percentage of recycled aggregates -		
GWP Transport -				
Load Number L001	Allowable Water Quantity 20 Cubic meter			
Time of Production 70.13 min	Time of Arrival at the Jobsite 16/10/2024 08:32:54			
Start of Unloading 16/10/2024 07:22:49	End of Unloading 16/10/2024 08:32:57			

Figure 6 Visualisation of order tickets in the user interface and in PDF format

3.2.3. Functionalities of the CEMEX solution

Figure 7 Assigning material to the element

Once the concrete is assigned to the element. We can enter "Material Take-off Tool", and search for the needed element manually or search for the type of concrete we want to order with help of "Material Name" cell. The other possibility is to look for the element using "Revit Element ID". Once we select needed elements it is possible to adjust the volume to of the order. If the new volume is 1.5 bigger than the original one, pop up window shows up with a warning for the user to be sure and validate final the quantity of the order.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Figure 8 Alert pop-up window, when ordered volume is 1.5 than initial volume

The "Material Take-off" window displays a table of elements and materials. The table has columns for Element Id, Family Name, Element Type, Material Name, Level, Quote, Volume [m3], and Order Volume [m3]. The total volume is 1012.96 m3 and the total ordered volume is 2.08 m3. A "GO" button and a "Create an order" button are visible in the top right corner.

Element Id	Family Name	Element Type	Material Name	Level	Quote	Volume [m3]	Order Volume [m3]
222668	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 6	<input type="checkbox"/>	9.97	9.97
223227	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 6	<input type="checkbox"/>	16.56	16.56
223441	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 6	<input type="checkbox"/>	3.94	3.94
259005	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	0.09	0.09
259034	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	0.46	0.46
259597	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	0.17	0.17
259625	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2.08	2.08
259698	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	0.53	0.53
259999	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	2.88	2.88
260028	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	3	3
260078	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	3	3
260107	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	2.89	2.89
260435	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	1.79	1.79
261073	Floors	MOS_Monolithic structural concrete (SLABS) 200	VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	Level 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	1.64	1.64

Total volume: 1012.96 m3
Total ordered volume: 2.08 m3

Legend
Purchasable materials
Non purchasable materials

Figure 9 Choosing element and material to order

For ordering the concrete from Revit we use help of already existing tool called Cemex Go. It is the transactional tool for concrete buying and ordering. During the Reincarnate project, we have created a possibility of ordering a concrete directly from the model. It helps to better estimate volume of concrete needed on the jobsite depending on the type of concrete specified inside the model, which gives us a direct translation of the emission of CO₂. The lower volume of concrete produced, the lower emission of CO₂.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Create order

1 Product Line Ready-Mix 2 Location 3 Specifications 4 Review

Select Product Line

Ready-Mix Bulk Cement Bag Cement

Aggregates

Exit Next

Create order

1 Product Line Ready-Mix 2 Location 3 Specifications 4 Review

Jobsite *
0082040532 Warszawa, ul. Pasteura/ Banacha

Point of Delivery *
Warszawa, ul. Pasteura/ Banacha

Purchase Order *
17.10.2024

Receiving Person *
Wojtaczka Wojciech 222507708

Special Instructions

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

🔍 Create order

1
Product Line
 Ready-Mix

2
Location

3
Specifications

4
Review

Product Specification

Customer: Mostostal Warszawa

Contract *

Product Description *

Quantity *

Unit *

Requested Delivered Date and Time *

Payment Terms

Unload Type

Application

Load Size

Clean Up

Additional Information

🔍 Create order

1
Product Line
 Ready-Mix

2
Location

3
Specifications

4
Review

Product Line, Delivery and Location

Product Line:	Ready-Mix	Delivery Method:	Delivered
Location:	Warszawa, ul. Pasteura/ Banacha		
Receiving Person:	Wojtaczka Wojciech 222507708		
Special Instructions:	Purchase Order:	17.10.2024	

Product Specification

00000000020238260 / VERTUA PLUS C30/37 S3 16H MPL XC4 XD1

Quantity	Delivery Date	Delivery Time
2.07920471146456	18/10/2024 17:32:45	01:00 PM
Contract	Payment	
1024400524	Credit	
Additional Information	Unload Type	
-	Direct	
Unload Time	Clean Up	Application
DT-SMI	false	Flooring
		Spacing
		5 min

Figure 10 Creation of the order in 4 steps

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Once the concrete is requested to be ordered, information goes to the concrete plant. Concrete is produced and then dispatched. Arrives at the jobsite at the agreed date, time and location. In the Cemex Revit plug-in it is possible to follow the status of delivery simultaneously. Available status are as follows: Confirmed, In process – Not Ticketed, In process – Loading (on the truck), In process – On Route, In process – On Site, In process – Unloading, Completed – Finished.

Welcome to Cemex Go For Revit

My Applications

- Customer Information
- Commercial Conditions
- Order and Product Catalog
- Apply to Revit Model

ERT HUB3

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Apply To Revit Model

Material Name: All | Order: All

Element ID	Element Name	Material Name	Volume [m3]	Assign
135185		VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	2.47	<input type="checkbox"/>

Order ID	Purchase Order	Delivery Date	Status
20607042	Test 13.09	13/09/2024 10:34	Confirmed

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Cemex Go For Revit

Apply To Revit Model

Material Name: All | Order: All

Element ID	Element Name	Material Name	Volume [m3]	Assign
135185		VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	247	<input type="checkbox"/>
Order ID	Purchase Order	Delivery Date	Status	
20607042	Test 13.09	13/09/2024 10:34	In process	
Ticket ID	Batched Date and Time	Total Delivered Quantity	Plant	Status More Info
39511036		1	PL-Kraśnik (Urzędów)	Not Ticketed More info

Cemex Go For Revit

Apply To Revit Model

Material Name: All | Order: All

Element ID	Element Name	Material Name	Volume [m3]	Assign
135185		VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	247	<input type="checkbox"/>
Order ID	Purchase Order	Delivery Date	Status	
20607042	Test 13.09	13/09/2024 10:34	In process	
Ticket ID	Batched Date and Time	Total Delivered Quantity	Plant	Status More Info
39511036		1	PL-Kraśnik (Urzędów)	Loading More info

Cemex Go For Revit

Apply To Revit Model

Material Name: All | Order: All

Element ID	Element Name	Material Name	Volume [m3]	Assign
135185		VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	247	<input type="checkbox"/>
Order ID	Purchase Order	Delivery Date	Status	
20607042	Test 13.09	13/09/2024 10:34	In process	
Ticket ID	Batched Date and Time	Total Delivered Quantity	Plant	Status More Info
39511036	13/09/2024 08:35	1	PL-Kraśnik (Urzędów)	On Route More info

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

The screenshot shows the 'Apply To Revit Model' interface. The left sidebar contains the CEMEX logo and navigation options: Mostostal Warszawa, Dashboard, Customer Information, and Commercial Conditions. The main area has search filters for Material Name and Order, both set to 'All'. Below the filters are two tables. The first table lists elements with columns: Element ID, Element Name, Material Name, Volume [m3], and Assign. The second table lists orders with columns: Order ID, Purchase Order, Delivery Date, and Status. The status 'Unloading' is highlighted with a red box.

Element ID	Element Name	Material Name	Volume [m3]	Assign
135185		VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	2.47	<input type="checkbox"/>

Order ID	Purchase Order	Delivery Date	Status
20607042	Test 13.09	13/09/2024 10:34	In process

Ticket ID	Batched Date and Time	Total Delivered Quantity	Plant	Status	More Info
39511036	13/09/2024 08:35	1	PL-Kraśnik (Urzędów)	Unloading	More info

The screenshot shows the 'Apply To Revit Model' interface, similar to the one above. The status of the order is now 'Completed', which is highlighted with a red box. The 'Unloading' status from the previous screenshot is no longer visible.

Element ID	Element Name	Material Name	Volume [m3]	Assign
135185		VERTUA PLUS C30/37 XC4 XD1	2.47	<input type="checkbox"/>

Order ID	Purchase Order	Delivery Date	Status
20607042	Test 13.09	13/09/2024 10:34	Completed

Ticket ID	Batched Date and Time	Total Delivered Quantity	Plant	Status	More Info
39511036	13/09/2024 08:35	1	PL-Kraśnik (Urzędów)	Finished	More info

Figure 11 Change of the status of the order

After concrete is fully unloaded from the truck, there are two possible ways to confirm receipt of the delivery at the jobsite. There is application for the driver of the truck called Driver App and there is application for the customer called Truck App. Nevertheless, what application was used to confirm delivery of the concrete, status of the delivery changes to "Finished". In this Reincarnate project a new development has been done to retrieve concrete delivery parameters from the system directly to the BIM model

Concrete delivery ticket parameters available in the Cemex Revit plug-in are:

- Project Name
- Jobsite Address
- Truck number or Vehicle identification
- Name of purchaser

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

- Plant name or Plant Identification
- Manufacturer
- Delivery ticket number
- Delivery date (DD.MM.YYYY)
- Time of production = time of loading (HH:MM)
- Time of the arrival to the jobsite (HH:MM)
- Time of the beginning of unloading (HH:MM)
- Time of the end of unloading (HH:MM)
- Consistency class or consistency target value
- Age of strength of class (days)
- Strength class
- Aggregate size
- Chloride content class
- Volume
- Exposure class
- Net Global Warming Potential (kgeqCO₂/m³)
- Gross Global Warming Potential (kgeqCO₂/m³)
- Percentage of recycled aggregates by weight (%)
- Special Properties

The screenshot displays the 'Apply To Revit Model' window. At the top, there are dropdown menus for 'Material Name' (set to 'All') and 'Order' (set to 'All'). Below these is a table with the following data:

Element ID	Element Name	Material Name	Volume [m3]	Assign
96458		RTUA PLUS C25/30 XC1	151.32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

A modal dialog box is centered over the table, containing the text 'Successful application of parameters on elements.' and an 'OK' button. At the bottom of the window, there are 'Refresh' and 'Assign' buttons. The left sidebar shows the Cemex logo and navigation menu items: Mostostal Warszawa, Dashboard, Customer Information, Commercial Conditions, Order and Product Catalog, and Apply to Revit Model. The footer includes 'ERT HUB3' and a copyright notice: 'Copyright © 2024 CEMEX Innovation Holding AG, Switzerland. All rights reserved.'

Figure 12 Assigning parameters to the element

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Almost all of parameters given above are required to be delivered to the customer by the European Standard for Ready-Mix Concrete EN206. This new feature created in Reincarnate project encompasses parameters required by EN206 and additional ones connected with the sustainability and circularity of the material such as Global Warming Potential and Percentage of recycled aggregates.

Figure 13 Parameters assigned to the element

3.2.4. Further development of Cemex tool

The development of CEMEX GO + BIM plug-in has achieved its goal in covering the whole workflow presented in Appendix 1. This means that completely new functionalities were successfully implemented and integrated with existing software ecosystem. Nonetheless, before the tool can be made available to customers there is still progress to be made to improve the plug-in's Technology Readiness Level (TRL). One of the fields for improvement is **making the tool more user friendly** by analysing the amount of steps that the users has to make to place an order and parametrise the model with order information. We recognise that for instance the choice of elements to be used for the Material Take-Off should be possible by choosing elements from

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

the model itself and not from the elements list. This functionality is foreseen to be added before, this solution is demonstrated at a Reincarnate demonstration site.

To make sure that the Cemex tool supports convenient parametrisation of the model it would have to be able to facilitate different scenarios in which multiple Concrete Delivery Tickets can be used to **parametrise multiple number of BIM elements**. This would assure that this functionality can be used for any type of a concrete order. This has been discussed already on the example of different concreting scenarios:

- Placing one big order for a part of slab
- Placing one order for a few columns
- Not enough concrete was ordered for one element and extra order was placed
- Concreting over several days

Based on this real-life construction scenarios required functionalities were identified to facilitate these scenarios. Currently the Cemex tool does not include this functionalities, but their development is foreseen.

Figure 14 Developed scenarios depending on the number of Concrete Delivery Tickets and the number of elements to be parameterised

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Another functionality that has already been discussed, but not yet implemented is the **parametrisation of the carbon footprint of concrete mix designated for disposal**. Though, the automation of the concrete ordering of the BIM model is supposed to prevent over-ordering of the concrete mix, there will still be single cases when either part of the order or a whole order has to be disposed due to human error. This creates the need for the functionality that will allow accounting for the concrete mix disposal in the plug-in. Here the challenge is twofold, the plug-in has to assign the relevant number of carbon footprint to something else than a BIM element. Additionally, the carbon footprint caused by the disposal process should be analysed closely, its value should be estimated and then it would have to be also accounted for in the plug-in.

One of the first ideas for the **ordering of concrete from** the BIM Model was to support this process with the use of a **4D Model**. This means that each model element to be concreted would include the schedule parameter such as a planned day of concreting. Potentially, this information could help greatly automatize the ordering process, by enabling the user to automatically carry out Material Take-Offs and receive Bills of Quantities with the exact date and time when concrete should be ordered. This could then be shared within the plug-in with the Concrete Manufacturer to agree on the Concrete Schedule. This would be a great support tool to support Site Engineers in their work. The only risk here is that integrating the planned work schedule in a BIM model is a laborious task on its own. Based on Mostostal's previous experience, the currently available technology for integrating the ever changing construction work schedule with a BIM model is ineffective and requires constant work on the BIM model.

Currently after the carbon footprint is parametrised in the BIM model it is up to the user to analyse and summarise it. An important extension of the plug-in would be adding **the functionality to create reports from that information directly in the Cemex Revit plug-in**. Here the ambition is to achieve a solution that would perform similarly as current solutions dedicated to LCA analysis. The competitive edge and the concept for new innovation is using the centralised carbon footprint data in the BIM Model that was saved in real-time directly from Concrete Delivery Tickets for complete LCA reporting of the concrete works. This has potential to be the most convenient solution in terms of amount of labour, as well as the most precise considering the source of the CO₂e values.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Cemex plan is to **test the tool in different European countries** – e.g. Germany and France in order to make tool more universal and robust. We need to see if the solution is working in different markets and is valuable for the different customers and their needs. We need to compare proposed concrete parameters for Poland with needed parameters for other countries. We need to understand if proposed type of delivery of parameters is the best one. Cemex would like to **make this tool available for its customers in the future.**

3.3. CP-IM platform

The CP-IM (Circular Potential Assessment Information Management) will integrate different solutions of the project with regards to assessing and facilitating the retention circular potential value in different processes (more information about the CP-IM will be published in D1.5 of the project). One of the integrated solutions is for the process of enrichment of IFC files with potentially valuable information for the end-of-lifetime phase of buildings, via Digital Delivery Ticket of concrete on site. The main rationale of this tool is based on the existence of specific information that are provided by concrete manufacturers and are useful for circularity assessments in the next phases of construction. This information is (or can be) available in a DDT. Therefore, there is a chance to transfer this information from the manufacturer to the building model when the concrete is delivered on site.

An important objective of T1.1 is to focus on capturing the gaps in the (under developing) circular processes that partners in practice are facing and have a practical approach in the selection of these gaps, and accordingly defining the problem, and finding ontology-based solutions. In this sense the approach to the use, methodology, and development of ontology has been “practice based”.

The function of ontology in these technical solutions for the defined problems (such as IFC enrichment by DDT) is to enable interoperability. An important success factor of circular economy in the built environment is the transition of information. Ontology in its nature is a formal description of knowledge and defines the concepts and relationships between them in a domain. Therefore, by developing and applying a piece of ontology, the required information can be interoperable.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

IFC as an open standard for building information modelling offers a good basis for interoperability between devices, stakeholders, and phases in the lifetime of the built environment.

In the development of the ontology pieces within T1.1, the IFC schema was reused, in the way that the defined entities and properties (for each solution) were mapped to existing IFC classes and properties, and new ones were suggested as possible addition to IFC schema.

By defining the problem, the main notions, relationships, and properties are identified. For example, in this case, concrete properties such as Exposure Class, and Carbon Footprint were identified as information that DDT includes and is important for the future circular scenarios, therefore is required to be stored in the building model. After the identification, the notions and properties are mapped to existing IFC classes and properties. Figure 15 shows examples of identified notions and properties in grey boxes, which are mapped (dashed lines) to existing IFC classes and properties, in purple boxes. To return to abovementioned examples, the exposure class of concrete exists as a property in IFC, however, Carbon footprint does not.

Figure 15 Example of main notions and IFC counterparts in purple boxes

MOS, CEMEX, and DEMO collaborated to define the problem, use case, and user stories regarding T2.1 (more information can be found in D1.1). The first phase of this collaboration included multiple sessions led by DEMO to define the problem and use case, which led to an ontological solution using IFC, and the second phase of this collaboration, focussed on the implementation of the solution, defining the user stories and technical requirements. In this process, CEMEX as a recycling company provided their digital delivery ticket, and MOS provided the information that they require to be stored in an IFC file which are useful for them in the future. Next to that, MOS tested the integration of the designed ontology, namely adding the properties

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

to a Revit model of their pilot building. Finally, DEMO has developed the tool, based on this use case. The tool includes the following services:

- A QR-generator in the CP-IM
- A database to persist property sets
- A mobile app (RE OnSite) to scan a QR code and handle user interaction
- A web service to search, scan and update an IFC file and facilitate database interaction
- A file server (SharePoint) to host IFC file

During the production or sourcing stage, the attributes and specifications of the product are clearly established and documented. Once the product is delivered, it is received, verified, and, if necessary, acknowledged with a signature by the accountable individual. At installation, the item is set up at a particular site and time, with the process carried out by the designated person in charge. To transfer the information, a QR code is generated.

When scanned with the RE OnSite iPad app, the product data is gathered and integrated with local information, including the current user, date, time, and location. The user then selects the corresponding IFC element via a 3D viewer and may be prompted to enter any missing details. Upon clicking submit, all collected information is immediately saved to the IFC file in the CP-IM repository, making it accessible to all authorized users and services.

Figure 16 shows the sequence diagram for creating the QR-code in CP-IM. Figure 17 shows the sequence diagram for creating the QR-code in CP-IM.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Figure 16: Sequence diagram for creating a DDT QR-code

Figure 17 Screenshots of scanning a DDT QR-code and updating an IFC-file in RE OnSite

4. Challenges and Opportunities

4.1. Revit BIM model creation – geometry focus

In the process of native model preparation, some challenges became present. The BIM model, initially prepared in the ArchiCAD program, was intended to be transferred into Revit software, for which the Cemex plug-in was developed. At first, the IFC model exported from ArchiCAD was opened in Revit, resulting in damaged geometry and with no information layer assigned to the model elements. Therefore, for the purpose of the REINCARNATE project, the native model of the building, Faculty of Psychology of the University of Warsaw was created from scratch in Revit, using the linked IFC model. This resulted in obtaining a complex building geometry with model elements additionally divided into concreting working areas on level 0 as a representative sample. The elements from this group were used for testing the developed Revit plug-in.

Figure 18 The output of opening an IFC file exported from ArchiCAD in Revit: a model partially exported with damaged geometry.

4.2. Revit BIM model creation – information layer assignment

The parameters to be applied in the IFC model were discussed at a previous stage of the [Task 1.1 Ontologies, information models, and inspection](#) and expressed in the IFC ontology prepared by DEMO Consultants. This ontology was also delivered as an Excel

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

file, and it was intended to be applied in the IFC model. Nonetheless, since both the solution working on the IFC file and the plug-in for Revit were considered in T2.1, it was found valuable to ensure that properties applied to the model in these two cases were comparable. Therefore, it was decided that the information layer of the Revit model would also align with the IFC ontology prepared.

Given the Excel file, the aim was to automate the process of applying properties to model elements so that if the ontology was modified, the information layer of all model elements could be updated correspondingly. To achieve this, MOS used Dynamo for Revit to ensure this automation by linking the script with the Excel file.

Include in IFC (MOW + CEMEX)	Cemex delivery ticket parameters
	Project parameters
Include in IFC upon upload of the model into CP-IM. No parametrisation based on Delivery Ticket.	Project Name
	Jobsite address
Not included in IFC	truck number or vehicle identification;
	Name of purchaser
	Concrete production/delivery parameters
	Plant name / Plan identification
	Manufacturer
	Delivery ticket number
	Delivery date
	Time of production=time of loading
	Time of arrival at the jobsite
	Start of unloading
	End of unloading
Include in IFC as element parameter based on Delivery Ticket.	Order number
	Volume
	Concrete (Material) Parameters
	Consistency class
	Consistency target value
	Age of Strength Class
	Aggregate size
	Chloride content class
	Strength Class
	Exposure Class
	GWP gross (kgCO ₂ eq/m ³)
	GWP net (kgCO ₂ eq/m ³)
	Special properties
Include in IFC as material parameter based on Delivery Ticket. Material should be assigned to an element.	Percentage of recycled aggregates

Figure 19 The IFC ontology prepared by partner DEMO - selected parameters crucial for model information layer

The workflow of the script was as follows:

1. Reading the Excel file and importing data from the appropriate Excel sheet.
2. Selecting the cells in the Excel sheet containing the parameters.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

calculation was created to enable the display of this information in Revit.

Figure 21 The Dynamo script for the calculation of 'GWP gross [kgCO₂eq]' and 'GWP net [kgCO₂eq]'

The script's functionality resulted in the creation of all parameters defined in the IFC ontology for Revit model elements. All parameters would be created as instance parameters in order to display them all together. Additionally, 'Concrete (Material) Parameters' were created as instance parameters, as an exception to the IFC ontology, where parameters from this group should be directly created as material parameters. Due to the fact that Revit does not allow users to create custom parameters and only allows values to be inserted into existing Revit parameters, this simplified approach was chosen instead of developing a custom programming script.

Figure 22 Revit 'Material Browser' interface, which does not allow users to create their own material properties.

All parameters were grouped into three groups (according to the IFC ontology): 'Project parameters', 'Concrete production/delivery parameters', and 'Concrete (Material) parameters'. These were created in the existing Revit parameter groups: 'Materials and Finishes' for 'Concrete (Material) parameters', 'IFC Parameters' for 'Concrete production/delivery parameters', and 'Data' for 'Project parameters'.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

The screenshot displays the Revit software interface with three parameter groups highlighted and annotated:

- Materials and Finishes (Teal box):** Concrete (Material) parameters (according to the IFC ontology). Parameters include: Age of Strength Class, Aggregate size, Chloride content class, Consistency class, Consistency target value, Exposure Class, GWP gross (kgCO2eq/... 2), GWP net (kgCO2eq/m3) 5, Percentage of recycle..., Special properties, and Strength Class.
- FC Parameters (Green box):** Concrete production/delivery parameters (according to the IFC ontology). Parameters include: Export to IFC (Yes), Export to IFC As (IfcSlab), IFC Predefined Type (FLOOR), IfcGUID (0hOAnXFA166BT6t9n...), Delivery date, Delivery ticket number, End of unloading, GWP gross (kgCO2eq) 6, GWP net (kgCO2eq) 15, Manufacturer, Order number, Plant name / Plan ide..., Start of unloading, Time of arrival at the j..., Time of production=ti..., and Volume 3.
- Data (Purple box):** Project parameters (according to the IFC ontology). Parameters include: Jobsite address, Name of purchaser, Project Name, and Truck number or vehic...

Figure 23 Parameters from the IFC ontology created as instance parameters in Revit and grouped into existing Revit parameter groups.

To sum up, Revit model parameters were created in an automated way, with the ability to adjust the parameter list directly from the Excel file. Then, only clicking the 'Play' button in the Dynamo Player in Revit is required.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Figure 24 The user-friendly usage of the Dynamo script for calculating the GWP of each model element requires only clicking the 'Play' button.

4.3. IFC model – information layer assignment

When faced with exporting a model from Revit to IFC, due to the inability to add parameters directly to the material in Revit (which could then be exported as `IfcMaterialConstituentSet` parameters, aligning with the IFC ontology), it was decided to add parameters directly in the IFC file. This attempt was made in `usBIM.viewer+` from ACCA. While it was possible to add parameters to model elements, assigning material parameters was not permitted. Next, an attempt was made to add `IfcMaterialConstituentSet` parameters in the Blender program using the Bonsai plug-in for Blender (formerly called Blender BIM), but an issue arose from the program side. As an alternative, it was decided to assign properties to the `IfcMaterial` using the aforementioned software and plug-in.

The Bonsai plug-in allowed the user to create `IfcMaterial` Property Sets and Properties within them. Blender and the Bonsai plug-in are constantly being developed as open-source and free software. Therefore, occasional unintuitive issues could be experienced when using these programs, as was the case here. At first, we found the way of displaying the properties assigned to the `IfcMaterial` unintuitive, because they disappeared every time after being added, despite still being assigned to the model material. It was later discovered that they appeared in the 'Material' panel below.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Figure 25 IfcMaterial properties editing panel in Blender - Bonsai plug-in: the previous unintuitive way of displaying properties.

After consulting with Blender developers, the UI of the IfcMaterial editing panel was upgraded based on suggestions from partner MOS, now featuring a more intuitive and accessible interface:

Figure 26 IfcMaterial properties editing panel in Blender - Bonsai plug-in: the latest plug-in version, updated after MOS consultations with the Bonsai plug-in developers.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Finally, material parameters were added to representative elements of the building, proving that it is possible to align with the IFC ontology using openBIM tools like Blender and the Bonsai plug-in.

Figure 27 The IFC model with the IfcMaterial parameters added to the selected model elements.

The successful assignment of concrete material properties (as IfcMaterial properties) in Blender using the Bonsai plug-in resulted in the properties being displayed correctly, not only in Blender but also in other software with the functionality to show material properties, such as BIMcollab ZOOM. As shown below, the information layer of the BIM model directly reflects the desired material data structure.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Beam				
Summary	Location	Material	PartOf	Clashes
Property		Value		
^ MOS_Stained monolithic structural concrete (BEAMS)				
Name	MOS Stained monolithic structural concrete (BEAMS)			
Additions	Fly ash, silica fume (5-10% by mass of cement)			
Additives	Plasticizers, air-entraining agents			
Age of Strength Class	28 days			
Cement Class	CEM I 42.5 R or CEM II 42.5 N			
Consistency class	S4			
Strenght development	Normal			
W/C Ratio	0.4 - 0.5			

Figure 28 The IFC model displayed in BIMcollab ZOOM with IfcMaterial parameters included.

4.4. Assigning properties – other practical tests of openBIM usage

In addition to the actions presented above, partner MOS made attempts to assign properties to model elements directly from the native model level. For this purpose, the bSDD (buildingSMART Data Dictionary) plug-in for Revit was used. It was confirmed that, with the bSDD dictionary defined and published in the bSDD service, all properties can be easily assigned to model elements using this plug-in. Moreover,

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

once the bSDD is defined, the classification can be efficiently reused across different BIM models without the need to recreate it from scratch.

For this project, MOS's internal classification was used for testing. However, in the next phase of the project, the bSDD for the Reincarnate project will be created, aligning with the IFC ontology developed by the DEMO partner, so that the plug-in can be tested on the project-specific model information layer.

Figure 29 The process of assigning classification to model elements with the use of bSDD plug-in for Revit – step 1 – selection of the element (structural column).

Figure 30 The process of assigning classification to model elements with the use of bSDD plug-in for Revit – step 2 – choosing the proper class from the bSDD dictionary and assigning properties and property sets.

use of existing tools. The planned development of bsDD will furtherly systematise and standardise the Concrete Parameters for the use of concrete ordering and model parametrisation.

3. **Delays and Errors in Data Updates** - BIM tools are often updated in real-time, but if the ordering tool does not synchronize in real-time or there are delays in data updates, the concrete manufacturer may receive outdated demand information. This can lead to the delivery of too much material or delays in delivery if demand changes dynamically. To address this a custom Dynamo scripts were prepared that allow simple and quick parametrisation of the BIM Model to assure its quality.
4. **Difficulties in Adjusting the Production Process** - BIM allows for the delivery of materials in precise quantities and specified times, but concrete production involves resource planning, and adjusting production to variable demand can be challenging. The manufacturer may have difficulty quickly responding to changes in the delivery schedule, requiring flexibility in production and logistics planning. This risk might have to be managed by developing additionally functionalities of the Cemex plug-in.
5. **Complex Logistics and Transport Management** - Concrete is a material that requires quick transport and delivery to the construction site at a specified time. Any delay can deteriorate the quality of the concrete. Testing the ordering system in conjunction with BIM must consider these logistical constraints, requiring precise scheduling and availability of transport resources. Thanks to integration of the current solution with the Cemex order processing system the Logistics and Transport Management of the order should not pose additional issues.
6. **Implementation Costs and Time** - Testing and implementing system integration can be costly and time-consuming, especially if employee training and adaptation of existing operational processes are required. For a concrete manufacturer involved in daily production, a longer implementation time can generate additional costs and disruptions in plant operations. The demonstration activities foreseen in Reincarnate should showcase the efficiency of the developed solutions to prove its positive impact on

sustainability and economic factors of the concrete ordering and carbon footprint reporting.

4.6. Challenges in applying the ontology – CP-IM

Implementing the ontology as the suggested way of modelling faced some challenges, when exporting IFC properties from a Revit file. However, this was solved by following another approach, which does not require the modeller to integrate the properties in the model with null values. The tool does add properties and values to the IFC model itself.

Figure 32 Fragment of ontology established within WPI regarding concrete parameters

The DDT can access the internet to retrieve product data but is currently limited to data within the CP-IM due to project partners' closed systems and lack of external integration. In the future, this framework could be extended to connect directly with external sources, enabling

5. Scalability and Planned Demonstrations

5.1. Scalability

5.1.1. Scalable to other construction materials and elements

To expand the implementation of Deliverable 2.1, Lean Construction Resource Planning, Task 3.2 also from the Reincarnate project can be leveraged. Task 3.2 aims to facilitate the reuse of building products and components—more specifically windows, HVAC systems, and façade elements—by supporting both those looking to reuse such items and those offering previously reused products for further reuse.

While Task 2.1 focuses primarily on concrete elements, the methods developed in Task 3.2 can complement it. Task 3.2 delivers process maps for using CP-IM (Circular Potential Information Management) in reuse scenarios and serves as a decision-making tool to guide architects and designers in choosing whether to incorporate reused products into new projects. One key factor in this decision is the amount of CO₂e saved by reusing a product or component compared to using newly manufactured alternatives.

The calculation methods from Task 2.1, paired with the parameters and tools from Task 3.2, will be presented in a dashboard format. This will provide architects and designers with clear, actionable data to make informed decisions about reusing materials, ultimately reducing the carbon footprint of their projects. Additionally, the data generated will support the development of accurate Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) models to be stored in BIM models.

The integration and testing of the results from Task 2.1 and Task 3.2 will take place in demo cases within the Reincarnate project, with the potential for further innovation. These advancements will enhance decision-making tools for architects and designers, contributing to more sustainable building practices.

5.1.2. Scalability thanks to open standards

IFC, as an open and international standard, enables end users to collaborate and cooperate regardless of which software application they are using. The choice of IFC as the basis for the development of the ontology and the tool, provides scalability for different use cases, and reusability for other users.

Updating and enriching the IFC will support several objectives. Within the project, this enhancement allows the IFC query tool to assess the model's circularity potential and environmental impact, using KPIs for evaluation. For instance, a predefined query can identify high CO₂-impact elements, and combined with real product data from the DDT, this can generate a dashboard with relevant indicators.

5.2. Initial demonstration/ validation plan

Disclaimer: The demonstration of the Lean construction resource planning innovation is foreseen in the second half of the Reincarnate project within the WP5 work. At the time of submission of the Deliverable 2.1, the demonstrations are in the planning and preparation stage. Therefore, this section serves only as an overview of the planned scope of demonstration actions.

To validate that the software tools developed within the Lean construction resource planning innovation an extensive testing is foreseen. The demonstration activities are planned to be carried out at 3 projects. 2 of those will make use of real documentation, though the testing itself will be done on virtual scenarios. During the virtual demonstrations BIM models from real, on-going constructions sites will be implemented. Additionally, one demonstration in real life conditions, during an ongoing construction is planned. There the aim is to show the whole workflow starting from placing an order from a BIM model, through order processing and delivery and finishing with model parametrisation with a Concrete Delivery Ticket information. Thanks to integration of the CEMEX's plug-in with existing software used to process the material orders, connecting to a relevant Manufacturing Plant and proving the whole workflow should be possible. Reaching this ambitious target would prove that the CEMEX plug-in is a mature solution at a high Technology Readiness Level.

The demonstration activities carried out as part of the WP5 will have to present quantifiable results. Considering that the developed solutions are parts of complex software ecosystems (Cemex's of the Revit ecosystem and DEMO's part of the CP-IM) it is fair to assume that there is a number of irreducible errors. Hence, it would be impossible to look for all possible errors. Instead the approach is to measure the success of the demonstrations with a list of KPIs for each pilot case. The primary goal of the validation will be the use of KPIs to provide a technical evaluation of the solution as well as a check on how these tools contribute to the REINCARNATE project

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

scientific, societal and techno-economic impact. Especially, underlining the contribution towards waste avoidance and circular reuse. Importantly, the user satisfaction will be measured to assure that developed software solves real issues and presents added value to the construction sector. Additionally, the demonstrations will be used to create dissemination materials to communicate REINCARANTE results to a wider audience thus promoting lean resource planning innovation.

5.2.1. Virtual Demonstration #1 – Faculty of Psychology

The new building for the Faculty of Psychology will have 8 floors, including 6 above ground and 2 underground, covering a total area of 26,600 square meters. It will house 30 lecture rooms, quiet study areas, a 400-person auditorium, and specialized labs for psychology research. Sustainable features include energy recovery systems, renewable energy sources, and energy-efficient installations. These eco-friendly elements are intended to meet the standards for BREEAM certification.

The construction of Faculty of Psychology for University of Warsaw has been chosen as a pilot site at the stage of formulating Description of Action for REINCARNATE. Due to the fact that the construction is projected to be completed at the end of 2024 and the concrete work has been long completed, this pilot case is only included in virtual testing.

This construction site uses a wide range of digital solutions. Many processes e.g. progress reporting, health and safety processes, defects are facilitated on a CDE platform utilising a continuously updated IFC models. Additionally, to report the progress of work regular 360 pictures were taken and a point cloud for the whole building was prepared. To facilitate the testing of the CEMX plug-in additionally a Revit model was prepared from scratch, as the original structure of the building was modelled in Archicad. The Faculty of Psychology BIM Revit model as well as the IFC model have already been utilised during the development of the software tools as shown in the Section 3. Development and Outcomes. This pilot will be continuously used to find and solve errors and defects in the software.

Figure 33 The view of an IFC model used in the construction and Revit model prepared specifically for REINCARNATE

One of the advantages of CEMEX solution is that in calculation of the Carbon Footprint of the chosen material, site-specific characteristics of the material is considered. This opposed to the mean values normalised for the EU provides the user with more realistic, precise data. To ensure that relevant, local material information is available in the software, a key step was to integrate the software with the respective materials library. This has already been done. Meaning that in the development process of the CEMEX tool both Mexican and Polish material libraries were integrated. For the Pilot #1 this means that the testing will include using:

- the materials that were foreseen in the design documentation of this building,
- the relevant carbon footprint values, calculated for these materials specifically.

The planned scope of the validation within the pilot case #1 is to cover the whole dataflow as presented in the CEMEX GO + BIM chart (Appendix 1). The process consists of 3 main stages: (1) Placing the order, (2) Processing the order, (3) Parametrisation. The stages (1) and (3) consist of completely new functionalities, thus they will have to be tested extensively. The order processing and delivery is also a crucial stage in the whole workflow. Yet, this functionality has already existed in the digital toolkit of CEMEX prior to Reincarnate. Therefore, the particular steps of this stage will not be analysed during the demonstration. Only the aspect of the data flow throughout the whole process will be considered here, meaning the demonstration will focus on the

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

assessment of the integration of stages (1) and (3) with the (2) stage. This influences the preliminary plan of validation (Table 1).

The two sides of the demonstrations process, CEMEX and MOS have already established a preliminary list of validation activities for the Pilot #1. The approach to setting up the validation plan was to present in sequence the activities to be carried out during testing. In addition, the test sample on which we want to verify the correct operation of the application was pre-set and the parameters to be measured were specified. The target that the software should achieve in order to pass the first stage of demonstration was also determined.

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

Table 1 Preliminary list of testing scenarios

No.	Relevant process stage	Sub-process	Method	Test sample	Parameters measured	Target
1	Placing the order	Take-off	Starting with single elements, verification if the plug-in creates take-offs correctly. Test for different types of elements (beams, columns, walls, slabs) with and without openings (20 elements in total).	20 elements	Volume assigned to the element Volume in the order	95% of elements have correctly interpreted volumes
2	Placing the order	Volume of the order	Choosing "big element" (> 8m ³) and checking whether the order volume is divided correctly in to the number of deliveries	10 elements	Volume of the order	90%
3	Placing the order	Volume of the order	Choosing multiple elements that sum up to one concrete delivery. Checking whether the volume of the concrete is calculated correctly	5 combinations of elements	Volume of the order	80% of combinations' volume calculated correctly
4	Placing the order	Carbon footprint parametrisation	The ordered concrete sometimes cannot be cast and it has to be utilised. Does the application allow accounting for the carbon footprint of the utilised concrete?	5 cases	Functionality should be proved	Accounting for the carbon footprint for utilised concrete's
5	Processing the order	Time	Measure data flow time. The flow of information between the Customer – Ordering application – Concrete plant should not take too long.	10 orders	Data flow time	30 seconds per communication
6	Parametrisation of the model	Human-readable data	Final information about carbon footprint is correctly assigned to the Concrete Delivery Tickets And to the BIM model. Both machine and human – readable. Test participants should assess the readability of the carbon footprint data in the Concrete Delivery Ticket and in the BIM model	5 people	Readability, Satisfaction, Linkert scale	80%

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

7	Parametrisation of the model	Carbon footprint parametrisation	Checking whether the carbon footprint of the element is then assigned correctly.	20 elements	Carbon footprint (in the BIM model)	
8	Whole process	Carbon footprint calculation	Checking whether the carbon footprint of the order is calculated correctly (the transition from kg/m ³ to kg)	20 elements	Carbon footprint (in the processing system)	95% of elements have correctly calculated carbon footprint
9	Whole process	Supporting functions	Saving the date of concreting (end of unloading). Using Exposure Class and Strength Class for filtering the materials should be used. Possible change of the calculated concrete mix volume to account for loses	-	Date of concreting, other functions should be proved	All mentioned functions are present in the application

5.2.2. Virtual Demonstration #2 – Waste Water Treatment Plant, Albacete

The Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) is located northeast of the city of Albacete (Spain). It treats wastewater from the city and two nearby industrial areas. The land parcel has a surface area of 73,184 m², of which approximately 12,400 m² correspond to the area where the old WWTP is located.

The current plant has been in operation since 1993 and has a biological treatment system using bacterial beds. As a result of the strong urban expansion process experienced in recent years, work is being carried out to increase the treatment capacity of the plant and to renew some facilities and equipment. One of the actions contemplated is the execution of new facilities to implement a new biological treatment.

Figure 34 View of the WWTP of Albacete construction works, Albacete

Water treatment plants are the perfect complex urban projects for demonstrating the wider applicability of REINCARNATE solutions. This pilot was specifically selected because it occurs the construction of new buildings and facilities, as well as the

D2.1 Lean Construction Resource Planning

demolition of some of the buildings and facilities that are currently in operation, making it an ideal setting. Additionally the construction of the biological reactor is ideal for the test of CEMEX GO Digital Integration to BIM Environment due to the amount of concrete that is planned to be used during its construction and also because of the geometry of this infrastructure to be built is not too much complex to ease the tracing and managing the location tracking of the material. The BIM model of the new facilities elaborated for Reincarnate project (IFC and Revit formats) is available for the tests.

Figure 35 Views of the BIM model of the biological reactor, Albacete

It has been established the following preliminary plan for the demonstration:

- create a Spanish library with concretes commonly used Cr
- create an account in testing environment in Cemex Go for Spain Cr
- agree on delivery ticket parameters A

Actual Testing

The list of Cemex delivery ticket parameters list is studied in order it could be extended considering the information that is usually needed in quality control works in Spain. For instance in the case of designation by properties, the information must always contain the compressive strength, consistency, maximum aggregate size and exposure class. Moreover in the case of designation by dosage, it must always contain the cement content (in kg/m³), consistency, maximum aggregate size and exposure class. If applicable, it must be in possession of an officially recognized quality mark.

Actual dosage of concrete shall include at least in the XC3, XC4, XD, XS, XF, XA and XM environments: type and content of cement, water/cement ratio, content of additives (if applicable), type and quantity of additives, complete identification of the cement, additives and additions used, identification of the place of supply, identification of the truck transporting the concrete, time limit for use

In order to check the range of values is within tolerance it is necessary to have the following data available: cement content by weight, If the concrete is pumped, the cement content (kg/m³), water content, additives content by weight, additives content by weight/volume, fiber content by weight.

5.2.3. Real Demonstration – Urzut

R

The extension of the machine storage park Urzut is a construction site planned to begin in first half of 2025. This construction project will be both financed and managed by Mostostal Warszawa, which gives a great freedom to apply innovative solutions and creates ideal conditions for testing of the Lean construction resource planning innovation. The machine square also conveniently houses the Mostostal Warszawa laboratory for material testing, which has already contributed to testing concrete rubble to support future RIENCARANTE demonstration as well as support WP3 work on material reuse methods.

Figure 36 The current state and the planned extension of the Urzut machine storage park

The planned expansion will include a new paved area and a small administration building. The application of the digital CEMX plug-in in practice, with goal of placing real concrete orders and parametrisation of models with the use of real digital Concrete Delivery Tickets is foreseen. This will be the first test of the CEMEX plug-in in the relevant conditions of a live construction site. Additionally, the use of tool developed within T2.1 will be coupled here with the informed use of recycled rubble with the use of WP3 innovations. In result, this demonstration will not only lead to reporting of the construction's built-in carbon footprint, but also will allow the assessment of the sustainability aspect of the circular approach towards concrete reuse.

Figure 37 Some of the concrete rubble samples tested in laboratory in Urzut within REINCARNATE

6. Innovation value

The developed concepts and solutions have a potential to substantially contribute to the advancement of sustainability and circularity within the construction industry. By facilitating the real-time tracking of the carbon footprint, these solutions support the construction projects in adhering to future, rigorous environmental standards. Therefore, promoting the reduction of emissions throughout the construction process. In terms of circularity, these tools effectively minimise over-ordering, thereby reducing construction waste generation by minimising the volume of materials that need to be disposed of. By digitalisation of the ordering process, the material supply chain can be more efficient and transparent in result promoting better communication and coordination between manufacturers and contractors. By centralising carbon footprint information in a BIM model, the developed solutions streamline data access, enhance transparency and enable more informed decision-making, which in turn drives more sustainable and efficient project outcomes.

6.1. Innovation value for Contractor – MOS

The innovation value for a Contractor lies in enabling automatic data flow and efficient parametrization with just a few clicks,. Thanks to automation of the Material Take Offs and generation of Bill of Quantities great streamlining of project workflows is possible. This approach simplifies compliance with upcoming regulatory changes, making it easier to adapt to new legal requirements. Additionally, the tools enable seamless management of concrete delivery tickets, ensuring that all relevant data is captured and organized. By providing enhanced information on sustainability, contractors can deliver more comprehensive reports to investors, highlighting the environmental impact and sustainable practices of their projects.

6.2. Innovation value for Concrete Manufacturer - CEMEX

The biggest innovation value for Cemex is that a presented solution is another entry point for concrete ordering. It improves visibility of more sustainable concretes in our portfolio, makes it as an easily accessible data for clients. It also increases digitalization and better data exchange with our customers, such as construction companies and contractors. We hope to be visible for our customers as not only concrete producers but also as a building solution partner within the new green economy construction sector.

7. Conclusions

The report not only presents conceptual frameworks, but also delves deeply into the subject of Lean Construction Resource Planning by developing two digital solutions. New functionalities in the CP-IM platform and the Cemex BIM + GO system bring these concepts into practical application. The developed solution enables CEMEX to introduce a new service for their clients, which promotes informed choice of material based on its carbon footprint. Moreover, carbon footprint data collection is simplified and made easier for general contractors thanks to effortless integration with the BIM model. By making the sustainability data available at the design phase, the designers are enabled to calculate carbon footprint accurately, supporting compliance with environmental standards. Importantly, by facilitating precise, streamlined material ordering directly from the BIM model there is potential to significantly reduce construction waste and enhance project sustainability.

These innovations have the capacity to transform LCA processes and represent a significant step toward enhancing project circularity. In the later stages of the Reincarnate project, these tools will be refined, further developed, and thoroughly tested through demonstrations.

Appendix 1. CEMEX GO + BIM - workflow process map

New functionalities developed within T2.1 in the Cemex ecosystem

